

CHILD MARRIAGE: A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF THE UNITED STATES, AFGHANISTAN, AND INDIA AS EXPLAINED IN UNITED STATES NEWSPRINT MEDIA WITH REGARD TO LAW, RELIGION, AND CULTURE

A Thesis By

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Abstract:

Child marriage is a bitter truth that affects the lives of many children around the world. This practice changes children's lives socially, economically, and mentally. Experiences of child marriage differ across geographic regions and vary based on many social factors including, but not limited to: law, religion and culture. While many researchers examine the causes and consequences of child marriage, the present study aims to explore media portrayal of explanations for child marriage as related to law, religion, and culture in three specific geographic regions: The United States (U.S.), Afghanistan, and India. I used qualitative content analysis to examine three major newspapers published in the United States for how they explain child marriage in each country selected. Findings suggest the practice of child marriage is most heavily explained around policy and legislation for United States, religiosity in Afghanistan, and culture—specifically the culture of poverty in India. Ultimately, the general public garners much of its information from newsprint media and, thus, this research has important implications for why and how the phenomena of child marriage is able to continue based on perceptions of the issue.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

LIST OF TABLES	iii
ACKNOWLEDGMENTS.....	iv
Chapter	
1. INTRODUCTION	1
2. LITERATURE REVIEW	4
Out Come of Child Marriage	4
Child Marriage Across Geographical Locations.....	7
Factors Influencing Child Marriage	8
Role of Media.....	13
Theoretical Framework	15
3. METHODS	18
Location Selection	19
Data Sampling	20
Data Analysis	22
Ethical Issues.....	24
Research Reflexivity and Positionality	24
4. ANALYSIS	26
How U.S. Newspapers Explained Child Marriage in the United States with Regard to Law, Religion, and Culture?	26
The Role of Law in Prevalence of Child Marriage in United States.....	26
The Role of Religion in Prevalence of Child Marriage in United States	32
The Role of Culture in Prevalence of Child Marriage in United States.....	33
How U.S. Newspapers Explained Child Marriage in Afghanistan with Regard to Law, Religion, and Culture?	35
The Role of Law in Prevalence of Child Marriage in Afghanistan	35
The Role of Religion in Prevalence of Child Marriage in Afghanistan.....	39
The Role of Culture in Prevalence of Child Marriage in Afghanistan	41
How U.S. Newspapers Explained Child Marriage in India in with Regard to Law, Religion, and Culture?	45
The Role of Law in Prevalence of Child Marriage in India	45
The Role of Religion in Prevalence of Child Marriage in India	47
The Role of Culture in Prevalence of Child Marriage in India	47
5. DISCUSSION & CONCLUSION	49
Discussion.....	49
Limitation	55
Future Research	56
Conclusion	57
REFERENCES.....	58

LIST OF TABLES

<u>Table</u>	<u>Page</u>
1. Phase One	24
2. Phase Two	24
3. Phase Three	24

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CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

Child marriage, the marriage of an individual under the age of eighteen (Raj et al., 2014), is a bitter truth that affects the lives of many children around the world. This practice changes children's lives socially, economically, and psychologically. This type of union is common in many locations around the world and despite the efforts of many organizations like United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF), the International Women's Health Coalition (IWHC), and the United States Institute of Peace Organization, this type of union remains prevalent.

Statistics suggest that approximately 10 million child marriages take place every year (Svanemyr et al., 2012) and UNICEF (2019) reported that, worldwide, 650 million women and girls are married before the age of eighteen. In Maharashtra, India, the Women and Child Development Department reported about a 78% increase in child marriages by September 2020 compared to the previous year (Paul & Mondal, 2021). Though these statistics do shed light on a global social problem, it is important to recognize that the statistics available are skewed, as some cases of child marriage go unreported. For example, the Human Rights Watch (2016) reported that some Syrian refugee families do not register their children's early nuptials in the countries where they reside so as to remain applicable for economic relief. The same practice has been noticed among refugees from Kyrgyzstan. Accounting for underreporting, it is important to acknowledge that actual rates of child marriage are higher than those reported.

Some scholars argue that this form of marriage violates human and women's rights (Koski & Heyman, 2018; Nguyen & Wodon, 2012; Wodon et al., 2016). Article 16 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights states that "persons must be at 'full age' when married and that marriage should be entered into 'freely' and with 'full consent' (Nour, 2006: 1645). In other words, any country that authorizes child marriage, violates the rights of many children (Nour, 2006). While child marriage is frequently discussed in the United States as being present in both Afghanistan and India, it does remain largely throughout the country.

In the United States, state marital laws were shaped by English common law (Child USA, 2018), and they produced a system in which gives parents legal rights to consent or oppose to their child's marriage while they are underage. The English common law system is an unwritten practice of legal traditions that are based on precedents set by legal decisions (Child USA, 2018). Child marriage is legal in even though under U.S. law, the marriage of minors is legal throughout the United States (Koski & Heymann, 2018), the majority of U.S. citizens remain poorly informed about the practice of child marriage in their country (Lawson et al., 2020). Approximately 248,000 children, as young as 12, were married between 2000 and 2010 in this country; most of these marriages were between young girls and adult men (UNICEF, 2019).

In Afghanistan and India, child marriage is illegal; however, both countries have some of the highest rates of child marriage in the region. A report by Human Rights Watch (2009) indicated that 57% of Afghan girls continue to be married prior to the legal age of 16 years, and 60% to 80% of these girls are forced into marriage (Raj, et al., 2014). Poverty, control over women's sexuality and patriarchal social-cultural norms are the main causes of child marriage in India (Paul, 2019).

The media plays a significant role in educating the public and shaping their knowledge of "social realities" (Smith & Searle, 2003). How a phenomenon and related information are framed, structured, and described shapes the understanding of a given topic. Brüggermann (2014, p.4) stated that "journalistic agenda setting, and frame setting can be viewed as the different ways in which journalists—deliberately, or not—shape news content". Journalists have the ability to change an individual's judgment, attitude, decisions, and knowledge by stressing certain news and holding back others (Semetko & Scammell, 2012). A country's legislation and policies depend on the level of the public's knowledge about a subject. Thus, public knowledge about child marriage is based on the selection and formation of a subject by, in part, news agencies. Lack of coverage skewed or limiting descriptions, and faulty knowledge about the practice of child marriage leads to the survival of this practice.

In this research, I address the following research question: How do U.S. newspapers explain child marriage in the U.S., Afghanistan, and India with regard to law, religion, and culture? I first begin by discussing extant literature about child marriage to show why this topic is an important issue and needs more public attention. I will also discuss Intersectionality Framework and how the interconnection of gender, religion, and culture with the legal system of each country, contribute to the marginalization of woman in selected regions and how each factor exacerbates one another. Next, I explain the method that I used for this study. Then, I discuss the findings of my analysis as related to each country and how newsprint media discussed the role of law, religion, and culture as related to child marriage. I conclude with a discussion of the implications from my work, limitations of the current research, and recommendations for future work in this area. Ultimately, the finding shed light on why child marriage remains an issue worldwide and points to why many Americans are misinformed about the practice, especially when it comes to their own country.

CHAPTER 2

REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

Outcomes of Child Marriage

Advocates and researchers suggest that child marriage should be prohibited worldwide, as it affects the victim's life socially and economically and has many repercussions (Nguyen & Wodon, 2012; Warria, 2017; Wodon et al., 2016). Some effects of child marriage include, but are not limited to, domestic violence (Kidman, 2017), husbands' controlling behavior (Nasrullah et al., 2018) involvement in sex trafficking (Boyce et al., 2018), and psychological disorders (Le Strat et al., 2011). Studies showed a positive association between child marriage and domestic violence (Hong Le et al., 2020).

Domestic violence is defined as any use of coercive control involving emotional, sexual, or psychological assaults on a former or current intimate partner (Karag Jahromi et al., 2015). Research suggests that the prevalence of marital violence or domestic violence is higher among individuals who marry as adolescents (before 18 years) compared to those married as adults (Raj et al., 2010). UNICEF examined physical domestic violence in over nine countries in Latin America, Africa, and Asia. In each country, women who married before they turned 18 had a higher chance of experiencing domestic violence (Kidman, 2017). In 2006, a national report on domestic abuse indicated that among 4,700 households from 16 different cities across Afghanistan, 90% of women experience at least one form of violence, and 62% reported that they experienced more than one form (Li et al., 2018).

Furthermore, in Afghanistan, approximately 2,300 women and girls attempt suicide annually due to experiencing violence (Li et al., 2018). Coercive control is rooted in social inequality and women's oppression and is a common act in patriarchal societies (Paul & Mondal, 2021). It also limits women's social and physical mobility, causing isolation and taking away their independence (Asling-Monemi et al., 2008). Studies find a strong relationship between power relations, controlling behavior, and domestic violence (Paul & Mondal, 2021). Differences in power and control dynamics between

the couple are the leading cause of domestic violence (Paul & Mondal, 2021). Spousal age gaps and power imbalances characterize child marriage, thus heightening the risk of domestic violence and controlling behavior. Research by Nasrullah and his colleagues (2014) indicated that in Lahore, Pakistan, 47.8% of married women currently aged 15–24 was married before turning eighteen. Additionally, one-third of women reported experiencing controlling behavior (31.8%) and spousal violence (31.1%) by their husbands.

Abdollah, Qureshi & Quayes (2015) consider child marriage to be a serious social problem; it causes “lifelong deleterious physical, intellectual, psychological, and emotional consequences for countless children” (Van Coller, 2017, p. 363). Among such outcomes, it also situates victims in a vulnerable position, to be exploited and used for sex trafficking (Boyce et al., 2018). This includes “domestic and international sex trafficking of minors, the production and distribution of child pornography, mail-order bride trade involving minors, forced child marriages, and the involvement of minors as strip club dancers and employees” (Franchino-Olsen et al., 2020: 1)

The United Nation (“Human Trafficking,” n.d.) defines trafficking as: the recruitment, transportation, transfer, harboring or receipt of persons, by means of the threat or use of force or other forms of coercion, of abduction, of fraud, of deception, of the abuse of power or a position of vulnerability or the giving or receiving of payments or benefits to achieve the consent of a person having control over another person, for the purpose of exploitation. The United Nations explained that trafficking does not mean necessarily traveling from one physical location to another, and it does not require force, coercion, or other forms of abuse of power if the victim is younger than the age of 18 years (Barnert et al., 2017). Victims of child marriage are used as prostitutes or in other forms of sexual exploitation (Barnert et al., 2017). In many countries like Afghanistan, emotional and sexual violence may be embraced under social norms (Qamar, et al., 2020). The culture of patriarchy and gender inequality enforce such norms; they are even influential and reflected in the marriage law of Afghanistan (Qamar et al., 2020). Additionally, gender inequality in this country is one contributor to prevalence of child marriage (Raj et al., 2014).

Victims of child marriage also have a higher chance of being exposed to sexually transmitted diseases, especially when there is a significant age gap between the two partners (Mourtada et al., 2017). For the purpose of this research, sexually transmitted diseases or STDs include herpes simplex virus type 2 infection, gonorrhea, or chlamydia (Nour, 2006). Scholars argue that sexually transmitted diseases (STDs) could enhance girls' vulnerability to human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) and human papillomavirus (HPV) (Nour, 2006). Nour (2006) argues that since men have to pay large dowries for girls, they must work for years to generate enough wealth for marriage. Consequently, these men are older individuals who have had multiple sex partners over the years when they decide to marry, making them more vulnerable to being infected with STDs and passing them on to their young brides (Nour, 2006). While outcomes such as trafficking, intimate partner violence, and experiences with sexually transmitted infections (STIs) are common amongst child marriages, circumstances, overall, differ across geographic regions and vary based on many social factors, including, but not limited, to religion and culture.

Another concern for victims of child marriage is the heightened stress and responsibility young girls experience, which they are not prepared to navigate either physically or psychologically. Scholars suggest that being married as a child is associated with a 41% increase in psychiatric disorder prevalence (Le Strat et al., 2011) and burdens many young girls with responsibilities they are ill prepared to manage. Young victims are denied the right to express their feelings about the coerced traditional practices, and they are incapable of defending themselves or standing up for their rights (Ahmed et al., 2013). Additionally, lifelong suppression of emotions heightens one's risk of psychological disorders, especially among victims of child marriage. Depression is a common psychological disorder among these children (Ahmed et al., 2013). Child marriage also increases early pregnancy and pregnancy-related morbidity, causing major physiological and psychological health issues in adolescent girls (Ahmed et al., 2013).

Child Marriage Across Geographic Regions

Child marriage is a major issue around the world, specifically in the developing world. However, child marriage is fostered, reinforced, and perpetuated differently around the world. Prevalence of child marriage differs between countries, with the highest rates found in West Africa, followed by South Asia, North Africa/Middle East, and Latin America (Lee-Rife et al., 2012). When considering the number of girls aged 10–19 across various countries, more girls are at risk of child marriage in India than in most other countries combined (Lee-Rife et al., 2012). Based on population size and high rate of child marriage in Bangladesh, India, Afghanistan, and Nepal, roughly half of the girls affected by child marriage live in South Asia (Lee-Rife et al., 2012). Different forces drive child marriage in U.S., Afghanistan, and India. Moreover, each country tackles the issue differently, which may perpetuate or dismantle the survival of this practice in their region.

Though there is a widespread belief among the U.S. public that this form of union only takes place in third-world countries, research suggests child marriage is a serious social issue within the United States, too; however, Americans are poorly informed about the subject (Lawson et al., 2020). Evidence suggests that in the United States, child marriages are lower among white non-Hispanic children than other racial groups. On the other hand, it is higher among children of American Indian or American Chinese descent (Koski & Heymann, 2018). In the United States, the practice of child marriage is legal in almost all states. In 2018, two states, Delaware and New Jersey, outlawed child marriages (Harmon & Blinder, 2018). Pennsylvania and Minnesota followed suit, and in 2020, they also outlawed the practice.

Afghanistan, which is located in the heart of South-Central Asia, is the home to fifteen million women and girls who experienced a high level of violence and gender-based discrimination (Raj et al., 2011). Scholars argue that oppression of women (Blum et al., 2019) and extreme forms of gender inequality (Kabeer & Khan, 2014) are deeply rooted in the Afghan culture. Rumble et al. (2018) found that the prevalence of child marriage is mostly in countries and societies with high gender inequality. The Afghanistan Demographic Survey and 2015 Health Survey, as cited by Blum et al. (2019: 371),

indicated that “among females between the ages of 20 and 49 years, 12.3% were married by the age of 15 years, 41.9% by the age of 18 years, and 62% by the age of 20 years”. A recent report from Amnesty International (2008), as cited by Gomez and Silverman (2014, p. 490), indicated “Afghan women and girls still face widespread discrimination, . . . domestic violence, abduction, and rape by armed individuals, trafficking, forced marriages, including every young marriage, and being traded in settlement of disputes and debts ‘*bad*’ or ‘*badal*’”. Thus, though child marriage is considered illegal in Afghanistan, the country continues to struggle with a high rate of child marriage.

Women in India also struggle with gender inequality (Batra & Reio, 2016). Socially constructed gender roles are deeply seated in the sociocultural framework (Batra & Reio, 2016). India struggles with gender inequality issues beyond just equal economic growth and access to educational resource opportunities; it is firmly anchored in India’s sociocultural fabric that has deep cultural and historical roots. Importantly, such sociocultural influences have spillover effects across all domains, including the organizational workforce and social and political contexts. This unquestionable influence is still accepted as a norm within the societal and familial periphery. Accounting for these influences, child marriage is widespread in India despite the implementation of policies and programs to eliminate the practice (Paul, 2019). Child marriage is an illegal act in India, but in many parts of the country, the prevalence of such unions is very high. Indeed, despite India’s Child Marriage Act of 2006 that prohibited marriages of females under 18 years and males under 21 (Seth et al., 2018), the country has the highest rate of child marriage in the world (Pandaya, 2015). The 2011 Indian census revealed that approximately 17 million children between the ages of 10–19 years are married (Seth et al., 2018). Raj et al. (2014) examined child marriage in India and explained that child marriage is more common among poor uneducated girls from rural areas.

Factors Influencing Child Marriage

Given the comparative nature of this thesis, I am approaching this section with consideration to geographic differences. Based on geographical locations, parents in different parts of the world have different reasons, ideologies, and beliefs for their children to marry early in life. For some parents,

early marriage is the only way to save their child from economic hardship, while for others, it is more a cultural practice than anything else. Scholars have looked at different geographical locations worldwide to find the most common factors behind this union. Studies show that some of the more common explanations for child marriages include experienced poverty (Nour, 2006), religious beliefs (Uecker, 2014), culture (Ahnosi et al., 2019), and the legal system that allow such unions (Maswikwa et al., 2015). Save the Children estimated that in the next five years, an additional 1.3 to 2.5 million girls are at the risk of child marriage due to poverty and economic hardship due to pandemic (Paul & Mondal, 2021).

Many scholars point to poverty as the root cause or motive for child marriage (Lee-Rife et al., 2012; Nour, 2006; Paul, 2019). In many regions, parents evaluate the cost of having children based on gender, and they consider girls an economic burden (Warria, 2017). Providing food, clothing, and education is costly. Ultimately, families consider girls as consumers rather than providers (Nour, 2006). In India, including in Bihar and Rajasthan, early marriage is mainly based on poverty. For some parents in this area, marrying off their girls early in life is their way to protect them from economic hardship. Research shows that coming from a socioeconomically disadvantaged family and being illiterate situate child marital partners in more vulnerable positions.

Paul (2019) looked at five different socioeconomic groups in India: poorest household, poorer household, middle household, richer household, and richest household. The measure of wealth was based on the number and kind of consumer items owned by a family. This included owning a bicycle or car, television, and dwelling characteristics such as flooring, roof material, sanitation, and type of drinking water (Paul, 2019). His research illustrated that the prevalence of child marriage among low-income households (0.318) is significantly higher than high-income households (-0.414). Among the middle-class group, the frequency of child marriage was slightly lower (-0.199) than high-income household (Paul, 2019).

Religion is another factor contributing to child marriage. Uecker (2014) used data from Waves 1, 3, and 4 of the National Longitudinal Study of Adolescent Health to conduct multilevel event-history

analysis, to examine how religion at both the “individual and contextual level” connect with early marriage. Findings revealed that individual religious beliefs partially describe attitudes toward marriage and cohabitation. Kohno et al. (2020) used a meta-ethnographic approach coupled with thematic synthesis and searched literature from nine databases, to identify the key factors influencing child marriage. They identified six main themes: human insecurity and conflict; legal issues; family values and circumstances; religious beliefs; individual circumstances, beliefs, and knowledge; and social norms. Many families referred to Islamic religious belief, which influences them to practice child marriage (Kohno, et al., 2020).

In a study in Pakistan, half of the participants (10 of 19) provide religious justification to defend their decision of agreeing for their children to marry early in life (Nasrullah et al., 2014). They believed that according to Islam’s teaching, parents have to marry their daughters as soon as they reach puberty. By doing this, parents can effectively protect their child from immorality, sins, and evils associated with premarital sexual relations (Nasrullah et al., 2014). Moreover, victims’ families rely heavily on religious leaders’ opinions and guidance while deciding on their child’s marriage (Nasrullah et al., 2014). Similarly, in Afghanistan, religious leaders claimed that child marriage could protect children from illegal acts (having premarital sex).

In 2017, the Rohingya in Myanmar experienced a mass displacement to Bangladesh in response to escalating violence in their country. As a result, an estimated nearly 1 million individuals from Rohingya were placed in Cox’s Bazar (Melnikas et al., 2020). Researchers noticed a high number of child marriages among refugees in the camp. Melnikas et al. (2020) conducted in-depth interviews ($n = 48$) and focus group discussions ($n = 12$) with Rohingya male and female adolescents and young adults (14–24 years) on identifying the cause for the high number of marriages. Participants in the research explained that the girl should get married under Islamic religious beliefs once she reaches physical maturity (Melnikas et al., 2020).

Furthermore, the scholars argued that although Islam was justified by participants as their ground for practices like child marriage, not all Islamic countries have high number of child marriages.

Melnikas et al. (2020) argued that other researchers indicated non-Islamic countries also struggle with this type of union. They concluded that rather than reflecting on a specific religious preference, a combination of poverty, religion, culture, group norms, and political vulnerability better explain the high prevalence of child marriage in the camp.

Culture and society also significantly influence the prevalence of child marriage (Lebni et al., 2020). Scholars argued that in areas where child marriage is part of individual culture, families feel pressured by tradition and society to marry off their children very early in life (Svanemyr et al., 2012). Often, such cultures place high value on female virginity (Lee-Rife et al., 2012); thus, child marriage is a way to protect their daughters from premarital sex (Svanemyr et al., 2012). Girls who remain unmarried for too long may risk damaging their families' reputation since society would question the child's "purity" and virginity (Lee-Rife et al., 2012).

Lebni et al. (2020) argued that "social customs, cultural beliefs, community encouragement, social learning, and gaining prestige and social support" can force individuals in a society to comply with their cultural practices. Nasrullah et al. (2014, p. 5) discussed some of the cultural practices in Pakistan that encourage the practice of child marriages in the country:

- Poverty, traditional practices such as WattaSatta (bartering bride for a bride),
- PaitLikkhi (marrying children before they are born or are still very young),
- AddoBaddo (marriage among tribes)
- Swara/Khooon, Baha/Vani/Sikh (girls given in marriage as a form of dispute resolution), protecting the honor of child and family, and lack of implementation of legislation in Pakistan.

In South Asia, including Afghanistan, a cultural practice called "*bad*" or "*badal*" (marital exchange between families or communities to resolve a dispute) is prevalent. This culture provides a condition for the practice of child marriage, in which some girls are engaged as early as two years old (Raj et al., 2014). Victims stay with their family until they reach puberty and after that, the marriage is consummated (Raj et al., 2014). Dowry is another cultural practice, which is the wealth (cash gifts, consumer items, jewelry) that a bride brings with her into the marriage (Banerjee, 2014). As the girls get older, the dowry decreases; this persuades families to marry off their daughter early in life (Nour,

2006). Some societies expect girls to get married very young and have children in early adolescence (Lee-Rife et al., 2012). Thus, child marriage is a form of financial transaction that may contribute to practice of such union.

Moreover, legal statute and law are important factors that can either halt or authorize the practice of child marriage in a region. The Commission on Population and Development (CPD) stated their concern regarding child marriage in its 2012 resolution, since it has an adverse, physical, psychological, and social impact on young girls (Svanemyr et al., 2012). As a result, CDP urged members of the United Nations to enact, enforce, and implement laws to raise the minimum age for marriage in their country, if it is needed (Svanemyr et al., 2012). Research revealed that the law only works if the particular government is consistent in implementing and enforcing the law in the given country (Maswikwa et al., 2015). Omidakhsh and Heymann (2020) argued that enforcing a law that prohibits child marriage may reduce the prevalence of child marriage if it follows a national campaign to educate the public and change social norms. They argued that previous studies indicated that egalitarian gender-based policies and law directly impact social norms involving women's equality and empowerment.

In one example, Maswikwa and her colleagues (2015) illustrated all members of the African Union signed the ACRWC (African Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the Child) act after lengthy discussions. Based on this bill, all Sub-Saharan African countries set the minimum age for marriage at 18 and made the registration of all marriage's mandatory (Maswikwa et al., 2015). Theoretically, countries in Sub-Saharan Africa are legally obligated by the terms of these agreements. However, evidence shows that the political will to change marriage laws varies considerably in each country, so enforcing the law was inconsistent (Maswikwa et al., 2015). Scholars explained that 37 of 41 countries in Sub-Saharan Africa (90%) had legislated minimum marriage ages of 18 or older for females. On the other hand, 12 of the 37 countries permitted marriage before 18 with parental consent (Maswikwa et al., 2015). Ultimately, child marriage was 40% lower among women in countries with laws that set the minimum marriage age for girls to be 18 or older in comparison to

women in other countries with more lax laws and/or enforcement. Maswikwa and her colleagues (2015) emphasized that implementing a law that require minimum marriage at 18 or older may protect against the exploitation of girls. However, Maswikwa and her colleagues (2015) added that other factors such as poverty and lack of education might influence public compliance.

The Role of Media

Gage (2013) argued that interpersonal communication and mass media play an essential role in individual decision-making. In the year 2000, Ethiopia established the legal minimum age for marriage (LMAM) at 18 and required that both parties give their free and full consent (Gage, 2013). In 2005, the new criminal code imposed a three-year prison sentence for marrying a girl aged 13 to 17 and a minimum of seven years if she is younger than 13 (Gage, 2013). Additionally, any person who solemnizes the marriage with the knowledge about the illegality of the act would receive a maximum prison time of three years or maximum fines of birr 5,000, which is about \$280 (Gage, 2013). In her research, Gage (2013) examined how exposure to mass media (radio and television) and interpersonal communication regarding child marriage prevention was related with knowledge of marriage legislation and parents' attitudes in delaying their child's marriage in the Amhara region. The analyses found that mass media effectively changes social norms if the message is consistent and comes from multiple sources (Gage, 2013). On the other hand, both interpersonal communication and mass media exposure regarding knowledge of the LMAM and parents' attitudes in delaying their child's marriage were found to vary significantly across communities (Gage, 2013).

Scholars identified newsprint media as a source for educating the public about the consequences of child marriage. Nwaolikpe (2018) explained that the Child Rights Act was passed in Nigeria in 2003, which puts the age of marriage at 18 years old; however, many girls still choose to get married young. She examined two Nigerian newspapers (The Guardian and Punch), which were published during the years 2013–2016, to examine how the concept of child marriage was discussed in the newsprint media and how the newspapers presented stories related to this subject (Nwaolikpe, 2018). Findings indicated that 57 (76%) of the stories were reported as news stories placed on the

back page. Eleven news stories representing 14.6% of the news stories were placed on the center spread page, while 7 (9.3%) news stories were placed on the front page. This shows that stories on child marriage were reported more on the back pages of the newspapers. Ultimately, Nwaolikpe (2018) found that there has not been enough focus on child marriage, and news stories did not explain the implications and consequences of child marriage to young Nigerian girls.

Furthermore, the Guardian and Punch newspapers' dominant theme on child marriage (39 news stories) was centered on the cultural and traditional issues surrounding child marriage. Stories on consequences of child marriage, which centered on consequences of child marriage which range from health, psychological, social, and mental issues, amounted to 29 (368.6%), and stories about child marriage being a child/human rights issue amounted to 7 (9.3%) news stories. The result indicates that cultural and traditional issues about child marriage were more eminent in the newspapers (Nwaolikpe, 2018).

Most of the studies focused on the consequences of child marriage, while little focused on using media in educating the public about these consequences. Media, especially newspapers, is one crucial tool that can be utilized in educating the public about the prevalence and outcome of child marriage in a country. They can also help to expose the legal loopholes placed by legislators in a country's policy, which provides individuals with ambition and permission to get engaged in child marriages. Additionally, they can raise awareness of the issue and prompt change. Scholars mostly ignore the role of media in the prevalence of child marriage. Greater acknowledgment from scholars is needed to determine how media can help in changing harmful traditions and cultural norms in a country.

To address some of the gaps in current research, I focus on the explanation for child marriage as presented by U.S. newspapers and draw conclusions, based on my findings, about the implications this has on the education and understanding the public holds about child marriage in the United States, Afghanistan, and India. My primary focuses are situated around the law/legal system

of each country, the way religion influences child marriage in each country, and how culture affects the phenomenon of child marriage within each country.

Theoretical Framework

For the purposes of this research, I draw on Kimberlé Crenshaw's Intersectionality framework to show the connection of law, religion, and culture in the practice of child marriage in the three selected countries. In the following section, I discuss this framework and its application within the current research.

Kimberlé Crenshaw (1989) introduced the framework of intersectionality to describe how different forms of inequality can work together and intensify one another. In other words, it is an analytical lens that helps to examine how different aspects of one's political and social identities can create situations to be discriminated against or to be privileged. Race, religion, cultural practice, cultural norms, and social class are among the social divisions on which people are judged. Gender is also a common aspect on which divisions occur. Taefi (2009) used intersectionality theory to illustrate girls' marginalization within a society. She explained the unique positionality of girls as both women and children within a society synthesizes and intensifies girls' marginalization (Taefi, 2009). The intersectional marginalization of girls (as a child with adult dominance and as a woman with male dominance) further denies girls' rights (Taefi, 2009).

In societies with a dominated culture of patriarchy, women face discrimination daily. For instance, in Afghanistan underage girls face social inequality, and gender discrimination based on their age and gender, culture, and religion. Warrior, (2017) argued in her research that parents view girls as an economic burden that led to early marriage of these children. Gender bias, and culture play a significant role in this type of mentality which is deeply rooted in many parts of the world like Afghanistan and India. As a woman, females still being discriminated and face injustice by men. Batra and Reio, (2016) explained that India's struggles with gender inequality are firmly anchored in India's socio-cultural fabric. The influence of this type of culture has spillover effects across all domains, including the organizational workforce and social and political contexts. Intersectionality frames the

interconnection of multiple marginalization to explain how power attaches to specific categories is exercised against others (Crenshaw, 1991). The legality of child marriage in the U.S. causes many children to face violence due to getting married early in life. The intersectionality theory explains that girls being discriminated against in U.S. based on their age, gender, culture, religion, and negligence of the legal system to protect young girls from early marriage, which make victims discriminated beyond what other girls feel their society.

Drawing from Crenshaw's intersectionality theory, this research examines how victims in the selected countries experience inequality due to child marriage and how oppression assists in the prevalence and sustainment of child marriage in each country. The application of this theory helps in analyzing how U.S newspapers define and compare child marriage in a western country (the United States) compared to Eastern countries (Afghanistan and India). Intersectionality facilitates a deeper understanding of the ways particular components of a given space, such as imperialism and orientalism, create power imbalances which occur in different forms of social inequality.

Edward Said described Orientalism as a way the West structures the Orient as the "other." Similarly, Burney (2012, p. 23) noted that Orientalism is the West's "social construction of the Orient, as the ultimate other in history, literature, art, music, and popular culture." Furthermore, according to Saada (2014), "Orientalism is based on structures of power, knowledge, hegemony, culture, and imperialism that work politically, sociologically, militarily, ideologically, scientifically, and imaginatively." In other words, how the West presents the East is based on an imperialist agenda; this is how the West controls the East. I use the concept of Orientalism to compare how U.S. newspapers present child marriage in Afghanistan and India compared to the United States. I employ this construct to show how imperialists use "othering" to downplay "Oriental" in order to control the region, that is, how journalists use the topic of child marriage to justify the United States' concern about women in the East.

Ultimately, utilizing intersectionality helps me to explain how the interconnection of culture, religion, and law in each country creates a power imbalance in which each factor intensifies how

people in each state experience social inequality based on their location. The image created by U.S. media which have a higher power in shaping and influencing people's knowledge about the practice of child marriage in each state, and comparing the issues caused by this type of union, is an essential part of this study.

CHAPTER 3

METHODS

I utilized qualitative content analysis to examine the trends, patterns, and themes emerging from the data in my research. Qualitative research involves collecting, analyzing, and interpreting data that are not easily reduced to numbers (Anderson 2010: 1). This method is used when research looks to describe and unravel issues analytically from elected individuals or population points of view to generate new "concepts and theories" (Mohajan 2018: 24). Using this method helps to focus on how the articles generate meaning (Hesse-Biber 2017: 249). According to Hesse-Biber (2017), qualitative data are rich in definition and offer several interpretations. In my research, I focused on what terminology is used by authors to describe individuals or what metaphors are used to cover child marriage in three different country. This is a vital part of my research to examine how journalists portray each country as related to the same act.

In this research, content analysis is utilized as the preferred method because I analyzed newspaper articles to find the common themes across three sources. Qualitative content analysis assists researchers in finding the meaning of concepts and words while explaining the relationship between them. This is done through a systematic process of coding and identifying themes. Qualitative content analysis is utilized for this research since this analytic system allows researchers to develop themes based on the recurrence of related information. This helps researchers to capture the underlying meaning in the text. In this study, each article will be analyzed to discover the message behind concepts and words used by authors in describing child marriage. The concept, words, or messages that appear more often can develop themes that can help me conclude. Parasad (2019) suggests that qualitative content analysis is used to find both subjective interpretation of data (manifest content) and objective elucidation of data (latent content). In this research, both manifest and latent content analysis were employed in different research stages, to capture the essence of data.

Location Selection

For this study, I selected three countries. The purpose of selecting three countries was to investigate how newsprint media frame and present child marriage in different geographic regions and how that, consequently, may influence public opinion and understanding of the issue. Additionally, it would help better understand the cause of lack of knowledge among the public about child marriage in these countries and examine if media have any role in this phenomenon. Furthermore, it could help determine what may lead to the public's misconception of the practice of child marriage in other states.

I chose India and Afghanistan based on two factors. The first one was finding countries with a high rate of child marriage and those receiving more substantial attention within the newsprint media. Despite the illegality of child marriage in both India and Afghanistan, they still are among the locations in South Asia with the highest number of child marriages. The other main factor in picking India and Afghanistan for this study was based on data availability. New York Times, Los Angeles Times, and Wall Street Journal mostly covered the prevalence of child marriage among these two countries. Although under India's Prohibition of Child Marriage Act of 2006, which established marriage of females under 18 years and of males under 21 years as a criminal act, child marriage remains extensive in the country (Seth et al., 2018). According to Pandya and Bhanderi (2015), India has the maximum number of child marriages, based on its population. Furthermore, their research indicated that in 47% of all marriages in these countries, the victim is a girl.

In Afghanistan, UNIFEM Afghanistan (2008) reports that 57% of Afghan girls continue to be married before the legal age of 16 years (Raj et al., 2014). According to the Afghanistan Justice Department, "Currently child marriage is not a crime in Afghan law but is prohibited under the Civil Code. Article 70 states that marriage is permissible when a girl is 16, and a boy is 18, while article 71 states that the marriage of a girl under 15 is prohibited" (Human Rights Watch, Afghanistan have a tougher law than Florida). As a result, United Nations put Afghanistan among the countries with the highest number of child marriages globally, especially South Asia (Raj et al., 2014).

The third selected country for this research is the United States, where child marriage is a legal practice (Koski & Heymann, 2018) in almost all the states. The minimum age for marriage varies (Koski & Heymann, 2018) and is set by each state. California are among the states that have no minimum age requirement for marriage. The United States is well recognized for showing concern about the violation of women's rights and child protection in other nations, while the right of many children is being undermined under the U.S. marriage legislation. I decided to include the United States in this research to examine how the U.S. media frame the practice of child marriages in this country compared to the other two locations. The information can shed light on why the public is not informed about this phenomenon and why they may have misconceptions about other countries, specifically India and Afghanistan. Selecting newspapers as my source for drawing the sample was based on two facts. Newspapers are considered as one leading source for the public to obtain knowledge and capture daily news. Additionally, the research question is about newsprint media framing; therefore, selecting newspapers was crucial for this research.

Data Sampling

For this research, I decided to choose the top three major U.S. newspapers to examine how child marriage is framed by geographic location. In order to do so, I implemented three steps. First, I identified the top three U.S. published newspapers. According to Journalism.org, *The New York Times*, with 82,639,256 prints, *Wall Street Journal* with 38,516,813 prints, and *Los Angeles Times* with 35,116,829 prints were among the top ten highest circulated newsprint in the United States, in 2018. Research by Yale University (2018) indicates that *The Wall Street Journal* and *The New York Times* have developed a worldwide reputation for thoroughness. *The New York Times* received more "citations from academic journals than the *American Sociological Review*, *Research Policy*, or the *Harvard Law Review*" (Hicks & Wang, 2013, p. 851). Additionally, the Missouri School of Journalism's research indicated that *The Wall Street Journal*, *The New York Times*, and *The Los Angeles Times* are among the most trusted newspapers among Americans (Kearney, 2017).

The next step was to ensure the selected newspapers covered articles about the prevalence of child marriage. In addition to the readership, I ensured the newspapers selected were reputable. For this purpose, I used the keywords to find any articles that cover the subject of child marriage. Related articles got filtered based on the date of publication and frequency of covering the topic. All articles related to the subject and published between January 2010 and May 2019 got selected. My decision for this date range was based on two factors. The preliminary research was done on the ProQuest newsstand by using the CSUF library site. The result indicated that between 2000 and 2010, a total of 10,221 articles regarding child marriage were published by different newspapers; on the other hand, between 2010 and 2019, around 101,322 covered this subject. That is an almost 91% increase, which shows that the subject of child marriage has gotten more attention from newsprint media within the last twelve years. The other factor was based on my ability to manage the number of articles that are getting analyzed. Given a large number of data initially identified, I utilized the following search keywords to filter articles further and increase applicability:

- child-marriage, child-marriages
- child-bride, child-brides
- underage-marriage, underage-marriages
- kid's-marriage, and kids'-marriages

Using these keywords was based on two facts. Preliminary research on ProQuest and CSUF library site indicated that some of the scholars use phrases like child bride (El-Mowafi & Foster, 2017; Lesson & Suarez, 2017) underage marriage (Kristof et al., 2018), or kids' marriage (Mcnamara, 2010). At the same time, I noticed that some of the articles used the plural form of specified phrases. In order to include all of the articles that covered child marriages in their print, I decided to include both the single and the plural forms of phrases.

The result showed 249 articles from the *New York Times*, 47 articles from the *Wall Street Journal*, and 99 articles from the *Los Angeles Times* (see Table 1). The outcome of the search was exported to an excel sheet to be more orderly and manageable. In the second phase, all the articles

that did not cover child marriages in India, Afghanistan, and the United States got eliminated from the spreadsheet. I extracted a total of 14 articles for India (NY Times, 7; WJ, 0; LA Times 7), 30 articles for Afghanistan (NY Times, 24; WJ 0; LA Times 6), and 86 articles for the United States (NY Times 42; WJ 15; LA Times 29) (see Table 2). In the last phase, editorial, op-Ed, commentary, book, letter, motion picture, book review, or TV program related sources were excluded.

Additionally, I removed any duplicated articles from the sample. The final sample included 25 articles referring to the United States, 30 articles covering Afghanistan, and eight articles about India (see Table 3). For this research, a total of 63 articles were read and analyzed. All the results were saved on the created excel sheet. The following section will demonstrate each phase in detail.

Table 1. Phase One

New York Times	Wall Street Journal	Los Angeles Times
249	47	99

Table 2. Phase Two

Countries	New York Times	Wall Street Journal	Los Angeles Times
India	7	0	7
Afghanistan	24	0	6
United State	42	29	5

Table 3. Phase Three

Countries	New York Times	Wall Street Journal	Los Angeles Times
India	4	0	4
Afghanistan	23	0	7
United State	10	4	10
Total	37	4	21

Data Analysis

The unit of analysis, or what is being studied (Elo et al., 2014), is each collected article. The first step during analysis was to decontextualize the articles (Bengtsson, 2016). At this stage, I read

each article in order to become familiar with the data and get a sense of the sample as a whole (Bengtsson, 2016). Next, coding was performed in two stages: first, open coding and then coding for latent content. Coding is a process that guides the researcher from data to the broader picture, which the author tries to portray. In other words, it is an analytical process used by researchers to interpret and make sense of the data. A code can be a “word or phrase that symbolically assigns a salient, essence-capturing, and/or evocative attribute for a portion of language-based or visual data” (Saldaña, 2016, p. 3).

During line-by-line coding, I read each article line-by-line and applied code to each line, in order to discover the manifest or emerging content and themes (Saldaña, 2008). The goal at this stage was to find any visible pattern or theme in the content (Erlingsson & Brysiewicz, 2017). A pattern is any visible consistency or repetition in presenting series of data. To further make sense of the first round of coding, the second round of coding was performed. Latent content analysis is more focused on the latent or underlying meaning of the context and allows researchers to look for the implicit meaning (Bengtsson, 2016). At this stage, I coded the text based on the message behind the text. The following section demonstrates a section of coding an article about child marriage in the United States. Foderaro (2017b), from the New York Times stated, “Since 1929, New York has allowed children as young as 14 to marry; 14- and 15-year-olds can do so with judicial and parental approval, and 16- and 17-year-olds can marry mere parental consent”.

The first round of coding: law, authority.

The second round of coding: acknowledging that law is old, victims are the helpless and voiceless, authoritative role of parents and judges in child’s life.

Next, I reviewed the results of both levels of coding to divide them into categories and subcategories. Codes that shared common characteristics or dealt with the same issue were placed under a specific category (Erlingsson & Brysiewicz, 2017). Categorizing the codes helps researchers compare and contrast each category with other categories; therefore, later on, each larger category can be divided into smaller subcategories (Graneheim et al., 2017). Additionally, using categories allows the researcher to limit evaluation and reach depth in justifying the issue (Hesse-Biber, 2016).

At this phase, I categorized codes that share a common theme in different categories; by doing so, I can discover consistent and undercover themes and answer a question like *why, how, in what way, or by what means* from the data. After categorizing codes, each category was divided into subcategories, to identify a common theme or message behind the contents. The following section demonstrates the category and subcategories of victimization discovered during the analysis of data.

Victimization Included:

- physical assault, violence against women
- exploitation, patriarchy, women as a commodity, misogynist, gender inequality
- abuse of parental authority

Ethical Issues

My research will focus on the analysis of newspapers. Thus, I have to make sure my research does not include any biases and only reflects the facts located in the data. Because my research does not include contact with any individual and only analyzes the public document, I had no need for IRB approval for this study.

Reflexivity and Positionality

As a Middle Eastern Iranian woman coming from a family in which child marriage was practiced for generations, I consider myself an individual who has a better understanding of how the culture of patriarchy, cultural norms, and religion can have a direct impact on women in West Asia. As a child, I witnessed how child marriage can affect victims socially, economically, and psychologically. My grandmother was nine years old when she married her husband, who was thirteen at the time. The strong cultural beliefs in this family led to pressuring my mother to marry at seventeen and my aunt at thirteen. Growing up, I witnessed my mom's struggles with mental health, which impacted me the most. My experiences in life, growing up with my mother, gave me a motive for this topic and research. It also gives me the ability to have a better understanding of how the intersection of cultural practices and social norms leads to women enduring marriages in which they feel unhappy. On the other hand, growing up in this type of family made me resent the women not seemingly willing to fight

for their rights. It also made me a defensive person when witnessing discrimination and social inequality.

Reading some cases of victims in this research was challenging for me. In some cases, I had to take a couple of days away from the data in order to make sure my experience with my mom and my personal beliefs did not affect my analytic judgment. In some cases, I had to read an article multiple times, in different timelines, to make sure my past did not influence my work. Due to my past, it was crucial that I make this research authentic and reliable; this made me focus on applying strong research practices and not on my past experiences. Additionally, in order to make sure my personal feelings and past experience did not affect my work, I had frequent meetings with my Chair throughout completing this thesis. Each section was reviewed multiple times and, ultimately, approved by her.

This topic was hard for me emotionally since children are the central point in this research. However, shedding light on the factor's newsprint media frame as strong influences toward the prevalence of child marriage in three countries made me continue. I hope my research can help other scholars interested in fighting this social injustice to look deeper into this matter, so that one day child marriage will be a story of the past. I believe knowledge is the best weapon that can be used to diminish this issue.

CHAPTER 4

ANALYSIS

How Did U.S. Newspapers Explain Child Marriage in the United States with Regard to Law, Culture, and Religion

The following section present the findings related to each country under study. I examine how U.S. newspapers discussed and described the roles of law, religion, and culture in the prevalence of child marriage in each country. Few articles in the study sample focused on child marriage in the United States, with most discussing either the success of New York's Governor Andrew Cuomo in raising the minimum marriage age in that state or the conviction of Warren Jeffs, the leader of the Fundamentalist Church of Jesus Christ of the Latter-Day Saints, as promoting child marriage by forcing a 14-year-old child to marry her cousin.

The Role of Law in Prevalence of Child Marriage in the United States

The law is a system of rules and regulations created by government institutions and/or authority figures in a country. These rules apply to all members of a society and are implemented in the form of legislation and/or policies. The newsprint media conceptualizes the prevalence of child marriage in the United States as a shortcoming of the justice system for recognizing and authorizing such unions under U.S. marriage law. In 2017, New York raised the minimum age for marriage to 18, although 17-year-olds can marry with judicial and parental consent. Furthermore, some states have no minimum age requirement for marriage and children at any age could get married with parental or a judicial consent (Foderaro 2017c). To highlight the issue, Foderaro (2017b), a journalist at *The New York Times*, stated that “across the country, laws allowing early nuptials are common.” By using the word “allowing,” she emphasized that this type of union is permitted and authorized by the U.S. government and is, ultimately, considered a legal act throughout the United States. Foderaro also used the word “common” to emphasize the normalcy of the legality of child marriage.

Journalists point out that both parental consent and judicial consent are ways through which child marriage can legally take place and, thus, may increase the prevalence of the practice.

Foderaro (2017c) and Crary (2016a) pointed out that “most states let 16- and 17-year-olds marry if

they have parental consent, and several states—including New York, Virginia, and Maryland—allow children under 16 to marry if a court official gives approval.” This demonstrates that the U.S. legal system widely permits parents to consent on behalf of their children and, in some cases, perhaps even force their child into an early marriage. And, importantly, the phrases “court official gives approval” also shows that this type of union takes place with the agreement of entities outside of one’s family—those that are at the institutional and systemic level. This shows that the act is considered legal at the state level. Perhaps most important is the built-in contradiction within the journalist’s framing here. Specifically, the statements indicate that the law recognizes 16- and 17-year-olds as minors—demonstrated by the fact that they must obtain consent from a judge or their parents to get married; yet they are seemingly considered mature enough to be married.

New York, in particular, has received quite a bit of the limited coverage around child marriage in the U.S. Governor of New York, Andrew Cuomo, justified the decision and stated that “the reasons [the state legislature feels] comfortable with the 17-year-old exception is there will be clarity that doesn’t exist now to ensure that all of the concerns have been addressed” (Foderaro, 2017c). Foderaro challenged politicians such as Cuomo who believe that a 17-year-old adolescent can freely consent to a marriage and argued that this perception is wrong, as “there is no way for a judge to tell whether a teenager is pressured by family members” (Foderaro, 2017c). In order to make their position clear, journalists used immigrants in the United States as an example to make their points.

Crary (2016b) stated that “in the United States, some immigrant families have retained those traditions of child marriage.” Foderaro (2017c) further contended that some immigrant parents retaliate against their children who refuse marriage: “If she tells the judge she does not want to marry, her parents will know she said that. We have seen parents fight back in many ways—locking a girl in her room or taking her overseas and forcing her to marry there.” Foderaro used the phrase “immigrant parents” to frame the practice of child marriage around immigrants in the United States. Foderaro then demonized these immigrant parents by stating that they are not concerned with their children’s best interests and that the victims face various consequences if they defy their parents.

She used phrases such as “forcing her,” “parents fight back,” “retaliate against,” “locking a girl in her room,” and “taking her overseas” to show some of the reaction’s children encounter from their parents.

Foderaro’s (2017c) article highlighted that child marriage via parental consent often involves coercion and that children remain silent about the pressure they feel because they fear being punished by their parents. Therefore, a judge cannot distinguish between a child’s free will or lack thereof in this situation. Foderaro (2017c) recalled a statement made by Fatima, a Muslim woman, about being forced to marry her cousin: “ ‘I was sweating and nervous,’ she recalled. ‘My mother was hitting me on my knee.’ If she had said no, she said, her father would have beat her. ‘They would have kept me locked up in the house forever.’ ” Foderaro used the phrases “hitting” and “beat her” to not only demonize Fatima’s family but also to show that Fatima’s fear of her parents kept her silent. Journalists identified immigrants as the social groups or “others” that practice such unions, subtly indicating that this practice is not common among “us.”

Furthermore, Crary (2016b) wrote that “states generally do not require any investigation of the possibility of a child’s coercion, and girls are often not asked if they are marrying voluntarily.” Crary raised multiple points to his readers to explain the problem with child marriage. He used the phrases “not require” and “girls are often not asked” to show that states do not feel it is crucial to investigate whether any coercion is involved in a child marriage case. In other words, he highlighted that the U.S. legal system fails to protect children’s well-being through negligence.

Although some states, such as New York, have a minimum legal age requirement for marriage, other states have failed to implement similar legislation. According to Foderaro (2017c), “more than two dozen other states have no statutory minimum age at all.” Foderaro first criticized most states for not having a “statutory minimum age” in place. By mentioning the lack of a statutory minimum age, she highlighted the age of the victims and their vulnerability. For example, the victim could be an 8-year-old child at the time of marriage. Foderaro mentioned New York to highlight the efforts some states made to stop very early nuptials. Ultimately, Foderaro’s article underlines the

ability of jurisdictions to raise the minimum age for marriage and, at the same time, the negligence of some legislators for not taking any action on this matter. Out of twenty-four articles which covered child marriage in the United States, seven articles just highlighted and talked about Gov. Cuomo's efforts in raising the minimum age for marriage in the state of New York. The frequency of coverage of this story is an indication that journalists highlighted lack of effort and concern of some legislators in implementing such law in their states.

Additionally, journalists discussed legislators' obliviousness and lack of knowledge about the practice of child marriage in the United States. In a statement to *The Los Angeles Times*, Fraidy Reiss, who campaigns against child marriage as the head of a nonprofit called Unchained at Last and who is connected to lawmakers, explained her encounters with some legislators. She stated that most legislators' responses to child marriage are, "I can't believe this is happening in my state" (Crary, 2016b). State representatives' confessions of a lack of knowledge about early marriage in the United States is an indication of why few legislators address this topic. Connecticut State Representative Michelle Cook was quoted as saying, "I was totally astonished that there is no minimum age in Connecticut for one to marry" (De Avila & Grayce, 2017). De Avila and Grayce (2017) highlighted the lack of knowledge of a state representative about the minimum age for marriage in her state. This indicates Americans' level of knowledge and how uninformed they are about important issues in their country. The phrase "astonished" shows that for Cook, her state not having a minimum age for marriage was shocking and surprising. In other words, she could not believe that such law exists in the United States. Cook's incredulity also implies that the media has failed to provide information to the public regarding important issues in their country.

Crary(2016b) also mentioned this issue in his article by stating, "Occasionally, details of child marriages emerge in news accounts." At the same time, Foderaro points out to lack of knowledge among Americans by stating Gov. Andrew M. Cuomo statement which said, "I don't think people even knew this, I think they are going to be shocked when they hear about the status of the law" (Foderaro 2017c). Using phrases like "don't even know" and "shocked when they hear" confirms a

lack of knowledge among Americans about the marriage law states in this country. Additionally, the statement implies that the failure of U.S. media is shedding light on such laws in this country. Crary wrote:

child marriage wasn't an issue of note for Virginia state Sen. Jill Vogel until she heard the stories circulating in her district about a man in his early 50s marrying a girl in her mid-teens, warding off a police investigation of his relationship with her (Crary 2016a)

By using the phrase “news circulating,” “lead sponsor,” and “reinforce,” Crary alluded to the importance of the circulation of news and of publicizing the issue to drive change in policies. This is an indication that legislators act only when a story becomes public knowledge; in other words, knowledge leads to action. Crary (2016b) stated that Vogel “heard the stories circulating.” This indicates that she heard the news through gossip in the office or from another individual and not from the media. The statement further reflects a lack of interest from the media in the subject and offers insight into the media’s view of child marriage as it relates to newsworthiness. Later in the article, Crary (2016b) wrote, “Now Vogel is the lead sponsor of a bill advancing in Virginia’s legislature that would sharply curtail child marriage.”

Furthermore, in the articles reviewed, U.S. newspapers positioned immigration agencies as a facilitator of child marriage in the United States for those who travel abroad to marry a child. Chatterjee (2019), for instance, focused on United States Citizenship and Immigration Services and its stance on child marriage. The Immigration and Nationality Act (INA) does not prohibit minors from petitioning on behalf of a spouse or spouse-to-be to receive immigration benefits, nor does it prohibit an adult U.S. citizen from petitioning on behalf of a minor spouse or spouse-to-be. In an article in *The Los Angeles Times*, Crary (2016b) noted that “the immigration services recognize the engagement of an adult with an underage girl.” He used the word “recognize” to emphasize the acceptance and acknowledgment of child marriage under immigration law.

This calls into question what defines “recognition.” In other words, is it right because it is a law? In another article, Chatterjee referred to an investigation by the Associated Press:

A recent investigation by the Associated Press found that the U.S. had approved thousands of requests by men to bring in child and adolescent brides to live in the United States over the

past decade. In 2013, for example, a petition was approved from a 71-year-old man for his 17-year-old Guatemalan wife (Chatterjee, 2019)

Chatterjee (2019) added that, “alarmingly, such approvals do not violate U.S. laws.” He pointed out several critical issues in the first sentence of his article. Chatterjee mentioned that the investigation was done by the Associated Press, which is an American nonprofit news agency. This shows the importance of the media in identifying social problems and educating the public. At the same time, it shows a lack of concern about the subject from many private news agencies. Moreover, according to Chatterjee, “the U.S. had approved thousands of requests by men to bring in child and adolescent brides.” In other words, U.S. immigration services do not have any problem with pedophilia; such an act is approved and recognized by this agency as legal. The use of the words “alarmingly” and “approval” are also crucial as they show that allowing such acts to take place under U.S. law is not only unsettling but also concerning to many.

In the articles analyzed, U.S. journalists explained the U.S. legal system as complicit in child marriage in numerous ways. A major criticism, as noted above, was the approval and recognition of child marriage as a legal act without considering child safety. In other words, journalists described child marriage in the United States as a result of the shortcomings of legislators who are aware of child marriage but decide not to act based on religious beliefs or the influence of religious groups. Immigration Services for recognizing the cultural practice of child marriage among some immigrants and allowing immigrants to travel to their home country, marry a child, and bring them into the country legally.

U.S. newspapers suggested that legislators build significant loopholes into the system to legitimize and encourage child marriage. Nevertheless, journalist also indicated that a lack of information among some legislators cause such laws not to be challenged or changed at the state level. The lack of knowledge extends to the public, which indicates that child marriage in the United States is a hidden subject. In other words, the media is not doing its job of educating people and exposing such laws.

The Role of Religion in Prevalence of Child Marriage in the United States

Seven U.S. newspapers highlighted religion and religious ideology as one of the leading causes of the failure to ban child marriages in various U.S. states. Journalists argued that religious groups and religious ideology have a strong influence on U.S. state laws—a situation they challenged. In 2017, Governor Chris Christie of New Jersey conditionally vetoed a bill that would ban marriage for those under 18. Foderaro (2017b) quoted Chris Christie as saying that “the legislation, which passed both houses of the legislature by strong margins, did not ‘comport with the sensibilities’ or ‘religious customs’ of some state residents.” Foderaro’s inclusion of the phrases “comport with the sensibilities” and “religious customs” indicates that the practice of child marriage is considered a custom and that banning it might affect some religious groups. In other words, Christie claimed that the acceptance of child marriage in the State of New York was based on respecting and being sensitive to certain religious groups. Moreover, Foderaro (2017b) stated that Assemblywoman Amy Paulin “had introduced similar legislation last year [in 2016, in Albany], but it had stalled because of concerns from some lawmakers who represent religious communities.”

Foderaro (2017b) further stated that “religious communities opposed the passing of the bill in two consecutive years,” pointing to the intersectionality of the U.S. legal system and religion in the passage of child marriage laws. She used phrases such as “religious community” and “opposed” to clarify that the religious community rejected the bill. By using the phrase “two consecutive years,” Foderaro pointed out that banning child marriage has been an ongoing battle between legislators and religious communities. This highlights the influence of religious groups within the U.S. legal system and the power they have in the passage of legislation. Foderaro also used the word “concerns,” followed by “lawmakers,” to show that legislators respect some religious groups that practice child marriage, that is, that U.S. lawmakers’ lack of concern about the lives of children who become victims of child marriage results from their thoughtfulness about other religions in the United States. Thus, religious groups are framed as the ones who oppose the passing of this law and as the root cause of the prevalence of child marriage in the United States.

Out of twenty-four articles covering child marriage in the United States, seven articles viewed Governor Cuomo's and Assemblywoman Paulin's success in passing laws that raise the minimum age for marriage as a significant accomplishment, as they withstood pressure from many religious groups. This indicates that the efforts of two legislators in banning child marriage and opposing religious groups were a significant subject in the United States.

U.S. newspapers described specific religious groups as the ones who practice this type of marriage, which is an indication that this type of marriage is uncommon in other religious groups. For example, Riccardi (2010) depicted Warren Jeffs, the leader of the Fundamentalist Church of Jesus Christ of the Latter-Day Saints, as promoting child marriage by forcing a 14-year-old child to marry her cousin. The topic of Warren Jeffs was seen as an important issue that was covered by *The Los Angeles Times* three times (2010, 2011, 2018), *The New York Times* (2016), and *The Wall Street Journal* (2015). This implies that journalists framed Mormonism as one of the religious groups that practice child marriage in the U.S.

Another U.S. religious group Foderaro targeted was Muslims: "Fatima H., an office manager in northern New Jersey, was 15 ... when her strict Muslim parents forced her to drop out and arranged a marriage to a first cousin arriving from Kuwait" (Foderaro, 2017c). Foderaro not only identified the victim by name, "Fatima H.," and her country of origin, "Kuwait," but also mentioned her parents' religious beliefs, "strict Muslim," as the motivation for the victim's early marriage.

Religion and religiosity were illustrated as the motives for many early marriages; they are also identified as a powerful ideological influence among politicians who oppose the child marriage ban in the United States. Religion is described as a factor influencing U.S. law and as a force in groups' cultural practices.

The Role of Culture in Prevalence of Child Marriage in the United States

Journalists described child marriage in the United States as a cultural practice among immigrants and conservative families. The interconnection of victim's culture, religion and law once again identified by the U.S. newspapers as the cause for prevalence of child marriage in this country.

Journalists described families who have immigrated to the United States find following their home countries' traditions and cultural norms essential. The concept of "othering" was pointed out again by U.S. journalists in describing the role of culture in the prevalence of child marriage.

According to Foderaro (2017c), "some immigrant families have retained those traditions of child marriage. In some cases, parents disapprove of someone their daughter is dating and pressure her to marry someone they view as more suitable." Foderaro (2017c) explained child marriage as a cultural practice among immigrants who are devoted to their cultural practices. In other words, this is a practice among immigrants and not all Americans. In the second sentence, Foderaro (2017c) stated that "parents disapprove of someone their daughter is dating" and "pressure her," which implies that the practice of child marriage is a way for immigrant parents to control a child's intimate relationships and sexuality. It is also an indication that parents try to avoid being stigmatized and criticized by their social groups by choosing someone whom they believe is the right person for their child.

Another cultural practice related to child marriage involves teenagers who have children out of wedlock. Foderaro (2017c) quoted Sonia Ossorio, President of the National Organization for Women New York, a group that has lobbied for the change in the law: "There have been cases where a girl is pregnant, and the pregnancy happened as a result of sexual assault." Foderaro (2017c) noted that in cases such as sexual assault and rape, it is not uncommon for a victim's parents to enforce child marriage. Foderaro (2017c) stated that they parents "are forcing her to marry because being an out-of-wedlock teen mother is a worse social standing than suffering a sexual assault in silence." Foderaro used "worse social standing" and "suffering a sexual assault in silence" to show how society's stigmatization pushes many families to force their children into marrying their rapists. She also used the phrase "out-of-wedlock teen mother" to illustrate that in U.S. culture among more conservative families, being a teenager and having a child outside of marriage is considered taboo, even when the pregnancy is the result of sexual assault. In other words, to maintain the family's honor, the child is forced to marry the predator. Journalists described being ostracized by society and the stigma of having been raped as a cause for the prevalence of child marriage in the United States.

By using the phrase “suffering a sexual assault in silence,” Foderaro (2017c) points out to the culture of shaming for being raped. In other words, the girls are viewed as the guilty party for being sexually assaulted and falling pregnant. She also framed parents of the victims as having their children suffer in silence to keep their status in society. In other words, for many parents keeping their status in society is more important than their daughter's well-being.

The dominant culture in each group dictates to its members what is considered the norm, and any behavior outside these normative practices is considered deviant and described by journalists as strange. According to journalists and media outlets, immigrants in the United States are the main group in this country who mainly practice child marriage. They use their children as a commodity and, in doing so, consider the norm based on their culture. For some families, falling pregnant in one's early teens is considered taboo and socially unacceptable, even if the pregnancy results from being sexually assaulted.

How Did U.S. Newspapers Explain Child Marriage in Afghanistan with Regard to Law, Culture, and Religion

Whereas articles on child marriage in the United State were limited, articles on child marriage in Afghanistan and India were much more prominent. Journalists within the United States blamed the Afghan government for not enforcing anti-child marriage legislation in their states. Furthermore, like for the United States, journalists pointed out the influence of religion and spiritual allegiance and the interconnection between law and religion as the causes of legislators' legal shortcomings.

The Role of Law in Prevalence of Child Marriage in the Afghanistan

Child marriage is illegal under the Afghanistan Civil Code, which declares that the minimum age for marriage for men is 18 and for women 16; however, despite legislative barriers, this type of union continues to be common and tolerated throughout the country (Nordland, 2018). One of the main issues noted by journalists is legislators' indifference to and lack of ideological unity regarding child marriage. The Afghan Parliament is divided into two main groups: hyper-religious conservatives and liberals who work with women's rights advocates to acquire more freedoms for women (Rubin, 2011c). The ideological differences between the two groups lead to negligence in uniformly enforcing

child marriage laws. The problem is further worsened by conservatives and religious leaders, who are more likely to favor child marriage, having more influence and power within the Afghan Parliament (Rubin, 2011c).

According to Rubin,

The Elimination of Violence Against Women Act was issued in 2009 as a decree by President Hamid Karzai. In a first for the country, it outlined basic protections from practices common throughout Afghanistan, including child marriage, forced marriage, physical abuse, and the practice of giving women in marriage to settle disputes between families, called *baad* (Rubin, 2013c)

Rubin (2013c) noted that the Act was issued in 2009, and under the presidential decree, child marriage is considered violence against women. She called this a “first for the country” and “basic protection,” which implies the government failure to provide women in Afghanistan with basic protection until 2009. Considered the first act related to women’s rights, the Elimination of Violence Against Women Act faced backlash from religious groups in parliament and religious leaders in Afghanistan. To gain approval, the Act was brought before parliament again in 2013, but it was sharply criticized and rejected by numerous government officials (Rubin 2013d).

Nordland and Sukhanyar (2015), in an article in *The New York Times*, explained child marriage saying: “the Afghan Constitution recognizes Shariah as well as civil law, but a presidential decree known as the Elimination of Violence Against Women Act (EVAWA) issued in 2009 [was] never ratified by Parliament.” The statement illustrates the problem with the interconnection between religion and law. Conservatives and religious leaders’ commitment to Sharia law overrides novel legislation. Although the Act is recognized and approved by the president, the members of parliament do not acknowledge the law based on their religious beliefs:

The anti-violence law is simply ignored in many parts of the country, and by some of its highest authorities—including Maulavi Baleegh (a prominent member of the National Ulema Council, the country’s highest religious authority), who considers it invalid (Nordland & Sukhanyar, 2015).

The statement indicates that the National Ulema Council has more authority than the president of Afghanistan, and that is why the act was never implemented. Similarly, Rubin said

angry mullahs and conservatives who never supported the law in the first place complained that it and the proposed revisions were un-Islamic and asked who could better decide than they who and when their daughters should marry (Rubin, 2013c)

Like Nordland and Sukhanyar (2015), Rubin suggested that the Elimination of Violence Against Women Act was never approved or recognized by conservatives and religious leaders, which implies that these groups are the ones who stand against passage of the law. By adding the phrase “un-Islamic,” Rubin pointed out that any law is passed under Islamic law, which is an indication of religious influence and at the same time justifies why child marriage is still a problem in Afghanistan. These groups believe the marriage of a child is not something that should be decided in parliament but that families should make the decision. At the same time, as they did not recognize the Act as lawful, they never enforced it in their territories. Furthermore, “who could better decide than they who and when their daughters should marry” refers to the child’s father. This statement is an indication that child marriage is part of Afghan culture and should not be challenged by legislators. Rubin (2013c) and Nordland and Sukhanyar (2015) illustrated that implementing the Act will not help to address and eliminate child marriage in Afghanistan and that working with religious leaders is the only way to end this practice. As child marriage is considered valid under Islamic law, it may be impossible for the government to ban and end such unions.

Journalists further noted that the religious groups and conservatives in parliament look for any opportunity to strike down the Act, which gives women more freedom and rights. Georgette Gagnon, then director of human rights for the United Nations Assistance Mission in Afghanistan and representative of the Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights based in Kabul, Afghanistan, described taking the Elimination of Violence Against Women Act before parliament as “fraught with all kinds of risk” (Rubin, 2013d). Rubin (2013d) pointed out that every time women’s rights groups take the Act before parliament to make the law more robust for protecting women and children, they risk losing all the progress they have made. Furthermore, the possibility is great that religious groups and conservatives will repeal the laws that are already in place. Gagnon used the phrase “all kinds of risk” to show the power of religious groups in the Afghan Parliament and

the possibility that the Act will be rejected outright. This also indicates why child marriage, despite being illegal, still prevails in Afghanistan.

Women's rights advocates explained their concern regarding making the law more robust, including the enforcement of marriage law, as a lack of trust in their government. Rubin (2013d), in an article published in *The New York Times*, quotes Soraya Sobrang, a women's rights activist: "We know who is in the Parliament." Sobrang was

referring to the former militia commanders, mullahs, and other conservatives who take a dim view of many Western-backed protections for women. What would stop them, she asked, "from pulling a list from their back pocket" of changes that would weaken the protections against child marriage or even rape? (Rubin, 2013d)

In the excerpt above, Rubin pointed out that Afghan conservatives and religious figures view the Elimination of Violence Act, which includes laws related to child marriage, as a result of meddling by the West and of the influence of Western values on their legal and cultural practices. In other words, Afghan conservatives and religious figures blame Western ideologies for the support for this pro-women legislation. Lastly, the author clearly explained the lack of faith and certainty among activists by quoting Sobrang when she speaks of "pulling a list from their back pocket." The phrase points out that activists know conservatives and religious groups can produce an array of excuses to repeal the law that protects women and bans child marriages. According to Huma Safi, an activist with Equality for Peace and Democracy, an advocacy group, "women are not on the agenda now. ... Every time we turn around, they're passing another law against women" (Nordland, 2014). The statement is an indication of the strong culture of patriarchy that directly affects women, including young girls, in Afghanistan. Rubin (2013d) argued that women in Afghanistan felt protected because of the presence of a Western country:

There are intensifying fears that the continuing withdrawal of international money and staff members ahead of the 2014 Western troop pullout deadline will leave women particularly vulnerable, after a decade of international attention made little headway in curbing some deeply entrenched and abusive Afghan traditions (Rubin, 2013d)

Rubin highlighted Afghan tradition as an abusive culture that makes women in that country feel unsafe and claimed that the only hope they have is the presence of Western countries. In other

words, the presence of foreign countries in Afghanistan is one way of protecting women in that country. She then quoted Georgette Gagnon, the head of the United Nations human rights division, who said, “With the drawdown in international assistance and support, there is a real risk that any advances in women’s rights will erode, and there’s already disturbing signs of that” (Rubin, 2013d). This statement indicates that any advances in women’s rights are the result of Western countries’ efforts and not of the efforts of government officials in Afghanistan. This article is a prime example of how imperialism and Orientalism work. Since colonial times, Western countries have used this method to colonize and use and abuse other countries.

The Role of Religion in Prevalence of Child Marriage in Afghanistan

U.S. newspapers highlighted the intersectionality of religion and law and their influence on the prevalence of child marriage in Afghanistan. Journalists suggested that most of the legislation passed or halted in Afghanistan was either influenced by religious groups or based on religiosity. The interconnection of the two resulted in slow progress toward the prohibition of child marriage and the enforcement of child marriage law in that country. The influence of religious groups and religious ideology in the Afghan Parliament is so profound that every time journalists talked about religion in Afghanistan, they referred to Islamic law, especially Sharia law, in Afghan legislation.

In response to changes to women’s rights law in Afghanistan, which include child marriage laws, Rubin (2011c) argued that the “government [is] pandering to religious and social conservatives as President Hamid Karzai’s administration starts reconciliation efforts with insurgents. Women’s rights, they fear, will be the first area in which the government makes compromises.” The phrase “pandering to religious” groups is an indication of the disproportionate influence of religious groups on the justice system. In this case, Rubin mentioned President Karzai’s name to show that even the highest power in this country tried to make amends with this group in parliament. The power of the religious group is so profound in Afghanistan that even women’s rights groups knew that ultimately, even the president of their country will compromise on women’s rights and safety to keep religious groups satisfied.

Journalists emphasized that conservatives and religious groups use religion as a weapon to halt any legislation that gives more rights and freedom to women. For instance, Rubin (2013d) indicated that when Afghan and international rights advocates tried to codify the law that outlaw's domestic violence, child marriages, forced marriages, and selling girls to settle disputes, religious groups in parliament protested that the provision is un-Islamic. The statement highlighting the notion that criminalizing child marriage is considered un-Islamic suggests that Islam is a religion that promotes child marriage. Qazi Nazir Ahmad Hanafi, a member of the Afghan Parliament, made a statement about the legal status of women's rights, including child marriage in Afghanistan: "This is an Islamic country and women will be treated and respected per the guidance of Islam, not some communist, secular conspiracy" (Nordland, 2014). The statement highlights several issues, including (a) the influence of Islam and Islamic ideology in parliament, specifically when it pertains to women, and (b) that legislation should follow Islamic law; otherwise, it is considered a communist plot. In other words, banning child marriage view as un-Islamic and influenced by communist ideology.

Rubin (2013c) focused on the relationship between religion and the legal system, specifically when the center of the discussion is women's rights, including the criminalization of child marriage. Rubin (2013c) restated a statement from mullahs (Muslim religious leaders) and conservatives to emphasize how the interconnection of religion and the legal system make child marriage possible:

The quandary became evident on Saturday when a bid to add more robust protections was rapidly withdrawn in Parliament after stinging rebukes. Angry mullahs and conservatives who never supported the law in the first place complained that it and the proposed revisions were un-Islamic and asked who could better decide than they who and when their daughters should marry (Rubin, 2013c)

Nasrullah (2014) et al. similarly emphasized the influence and role of Islamic beliefs in the context of child marriage. They found that according to the teachings of Islam, parents must marry off their daughters as soon as they reach puberty to effectively protect their children from the immorality, sins, and evils associated with premarital sexual relations (Nasrullah et al., 2014). Nasrullah (2014) et al. further explained that religious leaders claim that child marriage could protect children from illegal acts (having premarital sex).

Women's rights, including child marriage, is an apparently sensitive issue for conservatives and religious leaders in Afghanistan. Rubin (2013c) used the phrase "stinging rebukes" to show that giving women even a bit more rights is a heated subject that leads to strong rejection and criticism from conservatives. Furthermore, she noted that these people "never supported the law in the first place." As previously mentioned in the section focused on law, a central theme that emerged from the analysis is journalists depicting government officials and legislators as responsible for the lack of child marriage law enforcement in their territories. Rubin (2013c) stated that the government's shortcomings are based on considering the Elimination of Violence Against Women Act un-Islamic and illegal. Moreover, the reported statement from mullahs implies that under Islamic law, the father should have the right to decide to whom and when his daughter is to be married. King (2011) also explained religion as the main reason for the prevalence of child marriage, with "deeply conservative religious and tribal figures [are] opposed to a broad spectrum of women's rights." The interconnection of religion and legal system illustrated as one main issue in the prevalence of child marriage in Afghanistan. Women in that country are victims based on their religion and gender.

The Role of Culture in Prevalence of Child Marriage in Afghanistan

U.S. newspapers described culture as a cause of child marriage in Afghanistan. Journalists aimed at the interconnection of culture, religion, and law as one factor in the prevalence of child marriage. The influence of culture in dismissing child marriage law by the society is highlighted in many articles. In one of the articles, Rubin (2011a) explained Afghanistan as "a society where cultural practices are so powerful that few can resist them, not even the president," thus pointing out the strong and widespread influence of culture. She used the word "president" to show the power of culture over the most powerful person in the country, implying that the likelihood of changing cultural norms in Afghanistan is very slim. At the same time, the statement indicates how dedicated Afghans are to their culture and cultural beliefs.

In another article, Nordland and Rubin (2010) noted that child marriage is a part of cultural norms in Afghanistan:

The ordeal of Afghanistan's child brides illustrates an uncomfortable truth. What in most countries would be considered a criminal offense is, in many parts of Afghanistan, a cultural norm, one which the government has been either unable or unwilling to challenge effectively (Nordland & Rubin, 2010)

Nordland and Rubin (2010) illustrated child marriage as a standard practice among Afghans and underscored the strength of these cultural norms by stating that the government either has no power over these cultural beliefs or believes in the practice of such unions. This can explain why child marriage is so widespread in Afghanistan, despite being illegal. The statement further implies that an act that might be considered criminal in one country may not be viewed as a crime elsewhere and may be considered normal based on the culture.

When it comes to child marriage, the Afghan culture was presented as a vicious culture with no sympathy for women. In one article, Nordland quoted Manizha Naderi, New York executive director of Women for Afghan Women, in a discussion of legal restrictions related to child marriage:

Women at the shelters include victims (including child brides) whose in-laws, husbands, fathers and sons have broken their arms and legs, chopped off lips, tongues and noses, pulled out fingernails, sold them, stabbed them and left them for dead," Ms. Naderi said. "The proposed law would prohibit even the victims in cases like those from testifying (Nordland, 2014)

The story of Zahra, who had burns over 90% of her body when she was 14 and pregnant, was another heart-wrenching story told by Mashal from *The New York Times*. When Zahra refused to work in the opium fields, she was set on fire by her husband's family. When members of the public asked her father, Mr. Khaliq, why he allowed his child to stay in the marriage, his response was, " 'Why are you asking me? Go ask the Prophet,' ... explaining that they were merely following traditions from the Prophet Muhammad's time" (Mashal, 2016). Both stories present not only heartless individuals who do not regret their actions or have sympathy for victims but also a barbaric culture whose women are treated poorly and are unsafe. Nordland used phrases such as "broken their arms and legs," "chopped off lips, tongues and noses," "pulled out fingernails," "sold them," "stabbed them," and "left them for dead" to show what women, including child brides, experience in their marriages and how unsafe they are in that country. Mashal (2016) included a statement by Zahra's father, who

said he was “following traditions from the Prophet Muhammad” to show how vicious this religion is and how cruel her father was because he knew his child’s death resulted from years of abuse.

Additionally, U.S. newspapers framed the culture of poverty as a significant explanation for the prevalence of child marriage in Afghanistan. Poor families sell their daughters for financial benefits or financial relief. Nordland and Rubin (2010) quoted an advocate, who said,

Poverty is the motivation for many child marriages, either because a wealthy husband pays a large bride-price, or just because the bride's father has one less child to support. Most of the time, they are sold, and most of the time, it is a case where the husband is much, much older (Nordland & Rubin, 2010)

Nordland and Rubin (2010) supported the view that poverty may force many child brides into an early marriage. They used phrases such as "wealthy husband," "large bride-price," and "one less child to support" to show that money motivates families to push their daughters into an early marriage. The bride price is the money the groom must pay to his bride's family, which may influence parents' decision-making and increase the prevalence of child marriage. It also indicates that girls are viewed as a commodity within this culture, and for low-income families, selling their girls early in life is the solution to their financial difficulties.

Girls are also being used as a tool to settle debts or disputes arising from poverty. Nordland and Rubin (2010) shared the story of Naghma, a 6-year-old child who was used by her father to repay his debt. When the child asked him why he gave her away at six years old, he responded, "They said, 'Payback our money,' and I didn't have any money, so I had to give my girl." Nordland and Rubin (2010) used the phrase "didn't have any money" because it speaks to the culture of poverty. The phrase "had to give my girl" suggests that giving away his daughter was not the father's ideal choice, but he had to do so to settle his debt. The phrase "my girl" implies the dehumanization of his daughter, as he did not use her name or the phrase "my daughter." The father added, "I was thankful to them at the time, so it was my decision, but the elders also demanded that I do this" (Nordland & Rubin, 2010). The phrases "I was thankful to them," "it was my choice," and "the elders also demanded that I do this" illustrates several critical social issues. The patriarchal culture, inequality based on gender, victimization, exploitation of women, and being institutionally ignored by the

government are the most central themes that emerged from the statements made by Naghma's father. By including "elders also demanded," the journalists showed the hierarchical power in this country and the expectations to follow the demands of those in higher positions of power.

Speaking to the same points as Nordland and Rubin (2010), Rubin (2013a) wrote about this type of union and portrayed it as a cultural practice that occurs mainly in rural southern Afghanistan. Rubin (2013a) stated that those who grow up in these villages "remain bound by the tribal codes and elder councils, known as jirgas, that resolved disputes in their home villages." In this article, Rubin (2013a) noted that "the arrangement effectively values her [the child bride's] life at \$2,500." She explained that in Afghan tradition, the groom's family pays a bride price to the family of his wife-to-be. In other words, girls are sold and exchanged like a product. She used "elder counsel" to show the power hierarchy in that society; the same concept brought up by Nordland and Rubin (2010). Then she introduced the culture of "jirgas," which is a practice based on social inequality. The core concept framed in this statement is an indication of hegemonic masculinity that gives men in this society the right to exchange girls or assign a price to them to allow them to be sold like objects. This culture allows men to treat women like currency and use girls to settle their debts and disputes.

Further presenting the role of culture in the practice of child marriage in Afghanistan, Rubin (2013a) stated that the practice of selling children is "common particularly in Pashtun areas, but it exists among other ethnic groups as well and can involve thousands of dollars." She added that "even with some legal protections in place, Afghan women, and sometimes even little girls, can be sold to pay family debts." In the first statement, Rubin pointed out that this culture is widespread and does not belong to a particular country. Then, she employed the phrase "legal protection" to show that even implementing laws cannot override the strong influence of this culture. This implies that culture is the root cause for the prevalence of child marriage in Afghanistan and that the power of this culture is so strong that no legislators or legislation can change this system of beliefs. The commitment of individuals to their culture makes ending the practice of child marriage in Afghanistan almost impossible.

Viewing women as a tool to be exchanged like currency framed as one of the main reasons for child marriage in Afghanistan. In a research done by Warria (2017), she confirmed that child marriage is a form of financial transaction through which families can gain money for their daughter's hand in marriage.

People in rural areas in Afghanistan are more inclined and committed to their cultural practices based on limited education and the disproportionate influence of religious groups in these communities. The interconnection of culture and gender intensifies how they experience social inequality in the rural area than women who live in the capital of Afghanistan.

How Did U.S. Newspapers Explain Child Marriage in India with Regard to Law, Culture, and Religion

Child marriage is an illegal act in India but still, this country battles a high rate of underage marriages in the region. The prevalence of child marriage is discussed differently than U.S. and Afghanistan.

The Role of Law in Prevalence of Child Marriage in India

Child marriage is illegal in India under the Prohibition of Child Marriage Act, but like Afghanistan, this country has one of the highest rates of child marriages in the region. Journalists frame the lack of enforcement of this law as one cause for practice of such unions. To illustrate, Gettleman (2017), in *The New York Times*, explained that:

Indian law sets 18 as the age for marriage and consent to sex for a young woman. However, another provision of the law was inconsistent, saying a man could have sex with a girl as young as 15, as long as she was his wife. Advocates argued to the court that this exception encouraged child marriage (Gettleman, 2017)

The discrepancy between the two sections of the law indicates the inconsistency in the system. In one section of the law, minimum age for marriage and having sex is set on eighteen. In another section having sex with a minor is justified and legitimized if the predator marries the child. In other words, the second section of the law promotes child marriage which dismisses the first section. Gettleman highlighted the loophole similar to U.S. legislation in which it legitimizes a man's sexual relationship with a minor if the subject is married to the child. In other words, the law promotes

child marriage in order for men not to be punished by law for having intercourse with a child.

Advocates challenged the legal loopholes in court and eventually forced India's government to make amendments and strike down a code that permitted a man to have sex with an underage girl if they are married (Gettleman, 2017). Gettleman (2017) contended that persistence and challenging the law in parliament changed the legislation that involves children.

To prevent the practice of child marriage, India added a provision to the Prohibition of Child Marriage Act in 2006 that "imposes jail time, and a fine of up to \$1,500 for anyone caught participating in child marriage—but does not automatically render those marriages invalid" (Bengali, 2018). In his article, Bengali highlighted the consequences of breaking the law and showed that government officials are trying to impose sanctions. On the other hand, that the government does not dissolve the marriage is an indication of adding another loophole to the system to allow pedophiles to get away with having sexual intercourse with a minor. In other words, they legitimize the act by not consider it bad enough to intervene.

Furthermore, based on the Prohibition of Child Marriage Act, child brides are trapped in their marriages until they reach legal adulthood: "Under Indian law, married children can request an annulment up to two years after reaching adulthood, which it defines as 18 for girls and 21 for boys" (Bengali, 2018). According to the law, victims of child marriage are considered mature enough at 18 for girls and 21 for boys to dissolve their marriages. This implies that children can make decisions about marriage only at ages 18 or 21, so child marriage is not justifiable under this law. In other words, if child marriage is legal based on the age of the child, and girls at the age of 18 and boys at the age of 21 are considered mature enough to make decisions regarding marriage, the government should annul the union automatically, but Bengali (2018) noted that that government officials are hesitant to do so. This law also indicates that parents have the power to consent to marry their children, which is very similar to what the law in the United States suggests when it comes to child marriage.

In summary, journalists described the law as one cause for the practice of child marriage in India. They explained discrepancies between some of the country's laws as a reason such unions are permitted to take place. In other words, the legal system in India does not recognize and validate child marriage law since legislators created many loopholes in the system for men to get away with marrying a child and at the same time trap the child in a marriage that she might not consent to it in the first place.

The Role of Religion in Prevalence of Child Marriage in India

Religion was not framed as a leading cause for the prevalence of child marriage in India. Only the Hindu religious group was mentioned in *The Los Angeles Times* as practicing such unions based on religious beliefs. According to a 2011 Indian census report, there are six official religions in India, with Hindus making up roughly 80% of the population (Pew Research Center, 2019). Although child marriage is illegal in India, this tradition still prevails in different faiths. U.S journalists did not discuss child marriage among different faith in India, and only one article referred to Hinduism as the religious group that practice such union.

Magnier (2012) quoted a legislator from India's Hindu nationalist governing party, who said "child marriage was a way to stamp out 'vices' such as interfaith relationships." This statement indicates the power of religion among Hindus, with their religious beliefs overriding children's well-being. Children are pushed into marriage based on religiosity. Magnier (2012) quoted phrases such as "stamp out," "vices," and "interfaith relationships" to point out that this religious group considers their religion wholesome and holy compared to other religions, and in order to keep it secular, they promote child marriage. By forcing their children to marry early in life, they can stop interfaith marriages, which they consider sacrilegious. In other words, child marriage is a way for Hindu parents to exercise their power over their children to stop interfaith marriages. This statement also indicates the intersectionality of religion and politics within India's government.

The Role of Culture in Prevalence of Child Marriage in India

The culture of poverty was explained as one of the main contributors to the prevalence of child marriage in India. Journalists suggested that although child marriage is illegal in India, many families force their children into an early marriage primarily for the dowry. The practice of dowry is a common cultural practice among families that live in rural areas and/or who are poor (Gettleman, 2017). According to this cultural practice, the groom must pay a dowry to the bride's family to marry their daughter. Moreover, the younger the child, the higher the dowry. Nour (2006) confirmed this and explained that, based on Indian culture, as girls get older, the dowry decreases. This motivates families to marry off their daughters early in life and leads many families to force their children into early marriages.

Gettleman (2017) further noted that dowry is a way for a family to retrieve the money they spent on their daughter while she was growing up. Gettleman (2017) claimed that "many fathers are eager for the dowry payments they can get from men who want young wives." In rural India, low-income families often marry off their daughters in their early teens, as Gettleman noted (2017), to "men who want young wives." By using the words "eager" and "fathers," Gettleman (2017) underscored that in some families, the culture of marriage and culture of poverty cause many fathers to force their girls into an early marriage. He also used the phrase "men who want young wives" to illustrate the age of the child to his readers. By using the word "want," he framed the father as a brothel keeper who tries to make money from his child. That is, he framed the subject's father as a heartless person who willingly gives away his daughter to a predator.

U.S. newspapers pointed out that cultural beliefs are a cause of the prevalence of child marriage in India. This system of beliefs is deeply rooted in Indian society, and overcoming this practice is difficult. The articles portrayed Indian culture as a patriarchal culture based on social inequality and gender roles. Bengali (2018) described the life of Pinki Kumari, who "was only 16, but her fate had been decided much earlier, at age 4, when her parents had a wedding ceremony for her and a boy 10 years older and said they would live together when she grew up." Bengali noted that

weddings are often solemnized at very young ages. Then, brides are sent to live with their husbands' families, and the union is consummated in their teens. These cultural practices are deeply rooted in many communities.

CHAPTER 5

DISCUSSION

This research aimed to examine how U.S. newspapers discuss child marriage in the United States, Afghanistan, and India in terms of law, religion, and culture. I selected three countries to investigate how newsprint media explains child marriage to the public. The findings from this research shed light on how child marriage is portrayed and, as a result, points to why the public is not informed or is misinformed about this phenomenon in the United States and why citizens may have misconceptions about other countries when it comes to child marriage, specifically in India and Afghanistan.

The findings indicate that U.S. journalists discussed the legality of child marriage in the United States as related to the influence of religiosity and religious groups. First, journalists explained the legality of child marriage in most states. Then, they highlighted the efforts of specific politicians, such as Governor Cuomo of New York, in raising the minimum age for marriage in that state. Foderaro (2017b) quoted Chris Christie, former governor of New Jersey, who said that “the legislation, which passed both houses of the legislature by strong margins, did not ‘comport with the sensibilities’ or ‘religious customs’ of some state residents.” Thus, Christie positioned the legality of child marriage in the United States around the sensibilities of and respect for certain religious groups.

Journalists targeted the Fundamentalist Church of Jesus Christ of the Latter-Day Saints and Muslims in the United States as the two religious groups that practice child marriage. Foderaro (2017c) reported the story of Fatimah, a Muslim woman who was forced to marry to her cousin. By stating Fatimah’s faith, Foderaro indicated that child marriage is a common practice among Muslims. This can be the reason that so many Americans associate this type of union with Muslim countries. At the same time, journalists identified United States Citizenship and Immigration Services as one of the government agencies that facilitate and help immigrants to practice such unions by recognizing their marriages. By doing so, readers assume that this type of union is common among “them” and not

“us”; therefore, journalists portraying this practice as uncommon among average White Americans but common among immigrants leads to othering.

U.S. newspapers attempted to show immigrants as a group of individuals trapped in their old, traditional cultures while American politicians work to accommodate them by giving them the freedom to practice their traditions. This is a form of imperialism. Historically, Western media presented immigrants, especially those from the Eastern side of the world, as having inferior cultural and social norms. The images presented by these news agencies created a stereotype of people from the East being culturally old-fashioned and following traditions such as child marriage, creating a divide between “us” and “them.” This is the focus of Said’s *Orientalism* (1978). News agencies’ misrepresentation of immigrants and generalization of individual acts as part of traditional cultural practices among “them” is a strategy imperialist use to promote and advance their culture. This form of cultural imperialism, or “media imperialism,” is used mainly by the mass media to stigmatize other cultures and races to show the dominance of U.S. culture and to wield power over other nations (Elteren, 2003).

Furthermore, journalists described how uninformed most U.S. legislators are about the practice of child marriage. Crary (2016b) quoted Fraidy Reiss, who campaigns against child marriage as the head of the nonprofit Unchained at Last and who explained that most of the time legislators’ response to the news of child marriage in in the United States is “I can’t believe this is happening in my state.” Crary’s message to readers is that child marriage is legal because most U.S. politicians have no knowledge that such acts take place in the United States. Journalists underscored the efforts of Governor Cuomo in raising the minimum age for marriage by covering the story multiple times. This is an indication that U.S. legislators will act on banning child marriage if they become informed about such unions.

Moreover, journalists briefly explained that some child marriages are the result of teenage pregnancies. They noted that some of these pregnancies result from consensual sexual activities or sexual assault, which many religious and conservative families find shameful. Foderaro (2017c)

stated that parents “are forcing [a girl] to marry because being an out-of-wedlock teen mother is a worse social standing than suffering a sexual assault in silence.” The message readers receive from this article is that for some families, their social status is more important than their child’s well-being, and early marriage could counter the stigma.

To my knowledge, no research exists to show the interconnection of law, religion, and culture in the practice of child marriage in the United States, and this is the first study that focuses on how each factor contributes to such marriages. In line with Crenshaw’s (1989) intersectionality theory, U.S. newspapers described child marriage in the United States in terms of a lack of knowledge among legislators, immigrants practicing the culture prevalent in their home countries, and the interconnection of religion and the legal system. They also tried to show that the influence of religious beliefs and religious groups on some legislators may cause their shortcomings regarding this subject. They portrayed immigrants as practicing the culture of child marriage, framing mainly people from the Middle East as those interested in this type of union. The interconnection of religion and the U.S. legal system was positioned as a critical cause because both religion and law recognize and permit child marriage.

It is essential to point out the obliviousness of U.S. journalists in discussing child marriage in the United States. The topic seemed not to be significant enough to be covered and discussed by other journalists from other newsprint media in this country. Most stories that covered child marriage in the United States discussed either the conviction of Warren Jeffs, the leader of the Fundamentalist Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints, or the success of Governor Cuomo in raising the minimum age for marriage. This can indicate that either U.S. newspapers try to ignore the fact that this practice occurs in the United States and, importantly, that it is legal, or they do not find the subject interesting enough to discuss. At the same time, the subject of child marriage in the United States is an understudied topic. I could not find enough research on the topic. For example, this research builds on previous research (Koski & Heymann, 2018) that showed that the practice of child marriage in the United States is less common among White non-Hispanic children than other racial

groups, but higher among children of American Indian and Chinese American descent. To my knowledge, no other research has been conducted to confirm these findings. This lack of research indicates that this issue is important enough to be studied. Additionally, as a result, the findings in the current study cannot be confirmed by other studies, and this study might be one of the few studies focused on child marriage in the United States.

U.S. newspapers portrayed the phenomenon of child marriage in Afghanistan differently than in the United States. Despite child marriage being illegal in Afghanistan, the practice is prevalent. Journalists explained the cause of this practice largely around ideological differences between religious leaders and conservatives, on the one hand, and more liberal legislators, on the other, in the Afghan Parliament. The findings show a strong interconnection between religion, mainly Islam, and legislators and legislation in Afghanistan. This builds on previous research that found that within Islamic cultures, there is a high prevalence of child marriages (Melnikas et al., 2020).

Some of the journalists suggested that legislators who viewed banning child marriage as un-Islamic and against Sharia law failed to enforce such laws in their territories. Ultimately, the influence of Islamic ideology was characterized in U.S. newspapers as the leading cause of the prevalence of child marriage in Afghanistan. The story of Zahra by Mahal (2016) framed Islam as a vicious religion which their followers, like Zahra's father, are so brainwashed by their religion that even though he knew what her little girl was experiencing but based on the tradition from prophet Muhammad's time, he refused to save his child. This religion is blamed for prevalence of child marriage in Afghanistan and targeted for practice of child marriage in the United States by U.S. newspapers. This indicates targeting a religion rather than focusing on the main issue. Islam was pictured as an evil religion, and its followers described as bunch of savages who torture and abuse their women based on religiosity. This while no other religion targeted by journalists when it comes to U.S. and India. By framing the religion in this way, the message sent to the readers of these articles identifies Islam, especially Shariah law, as the cause for the prevalence of child marriage in Afghanistan. It also implies that Islam is the religion that promotes such unions. Consequently, many Americans associate child

marriage with Muslim countries. The information relayed to the readers gives them the assumption that this type of union is an issue in that part of the world, and it does not concern “us.” Drawing from Edward Said’s Orientalism concept, Islam was targeted by Western newspapers in order to show readers the superiority of “our” religion vs. “them.” In other words, “our” religion does not promote such a union, but “their” religion does. We have value, and we are concern with Women’s rights, by they do not. Stigmatizing a culture, religion, and beliefs is how imperialists justify their meddling in other countries.

When it comes to child marriage, the Afghan culture was presented as a vicious culture with no sympathy for women. Nordland (2014) used brutal details of what women (including child brides) in shelters encountered. There is no argument that violence against women in Afghanistan is pervasive, but this is a reality for many women in other parts of the world. Targeting a countries culture and explaining chilling details of what little girls experienced while there are many cases of violence against women taking place in Western countries, including United States, is nothing more than stigmatizing a country.

Scholars have studied culture and how effective it can be in forcing individuals to comply with social norms. Lebni et al. (2020) argued that “social customs, cultural beliefs, community encouragement, social learning, and gaining prestige and social support” can force individuals in a society to comply with cultural practices. There is no argument that culture plays a significant role in one’s behavior, but how a subject is explained or presented to an audience can also play a considerable role in people’s judgment and behavior. The way journalists presented Afghan culture to their readers created an image of Afghan women playing a submissive role and men in that country being savages with no sympathy or remorse when it comes to their women. Nevertheless, women, especially child brides, in the United States face violence regularly, but U.S. newspaper are hesitant to focus on these victims and tell their stories.

The dichotomy in presenting the topic of child marriage reflects that this social problem is manipulated as part of the “us versus them” narrative. This indicates that U.S. newspapers tried to

portray Afghan culture as abusive and tell their readers that this type of violence occurs only in underdeveloped or non-Western countries. At the same, these journalists tried to show how concerning these issues are for the United States. In the imperialist system, colonizers used excuses to explain their presence in colonized regions—Western countries used reasons such as protecting human rights, saving a country from its oppressor, and performing missionary acts to justify their actions.

At the same time, child marriage was shown as a cultural practice, occurring most prominently in rural areas. High levels of poverty and the patriarchal culture in Afghanistan were also explained as causes for child marriage. The inclusion of these facets of culture within newspaper articles about child marriage in Afghanistan aligns with extant literature describing cultural practices such as *Badal* and dowry, which, in some cases, result from poverty and thus influence the prevalence of child marriage in Afghanistan. This built on previous studies by Raj et al. (2014) that found in South Asia, including Afghanistan, a cultural practice called *bad* or *Badal* (marital exchange between families or communities to resolve a dispute) is prevalent. This culture provides a condition for the practice of child marriage, in which some girls are engaged as early as two years old (Raj et al., 2014). The interconnection of culture and religion was positioned as the leading cause for child marriage in Afghanistan. Overall Afghanistan portrayed as a country in which their people are still stuck in their old age traditions, and their religious beliefs override their common sense when it comes to the marriage of their children. The people in rural areas controlled by their religious leaders and lack of education and access to resources make them more vulnerable to be influenced by these religious groups.

While journalists wrote about the legal system and religion as primary explanatory factors for child marriage in the United States and Afghanistan, respectively, U.S. newspapers characterized the occurrence of child marriage as a result of the culture of poverty, specifically, in India. Although child marriage is illegal in India, the country has one of the highest rates of child marriage globally (Pandaya, 2015). Journalists, in articles included in the study sample, pointed out that legislators try

to enforce the law through fines and imprisonment for those who violate the law. Nevertheless, poverty drives many families to involve their children in child marriage as a means of obtaining a dowry. This finding parallels the work of previous scholars, who contended that the high rate of poverty in India is a cause of the prevalence of child marriage (Paul, 2019). Although few articles in the sample discussed child marriage in India, the legal system and religion were not characterized as leading causes for this practice.

Both journalists and researchers showed that this practice is more common in rural areas (Raj et al., 2014). Based on Crenshaw's (1989) intersectionality theory, child marriage rates are higher in these areas based on gender and the culture of poverty, which make the experience of social inequality prevalent in India more intense for women who live in more remote areas than for those who live in the capital. People in these areas are more economically disadvantaged and have less access to resources. Dowries and "bride price" are two reasons identified as the cause for this type of union.

Limitations

The limitations of this research relate to finding suitable articles on child marriage in the countries selected in the data collected from *The New York Times*, *The Los Angeles Times*, and *The Wall Street Journal*. When it comes to United States, most articles about child marriage in the United States discussed two stories: raising the minimum age for marriage in New York and the story of Warren Jeffs, the leader of the Fundamentalist Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints. Many other articles included in the final list mentioned child marriage in relation to charity, school projects, or other unrelated subjects that could not be used for the analysis.

Another limitation I faced in this research was the number of articles that dealt with child marriage in Afghanistan and India. For example, most of the only 30 articles about the subject of child marriage in Afghanistan focused on victims' life stories and the closing of women's shelters. Child brides often flee the abusive relationship and find refuge in women's shelters. The articles focused on the fight between religious groups and a women's rights group in Afghanistan over closing these

shelters, considered home by many child brides. Additionally, few articles were available for India. The topic of child marriage in India was rarely discussed in U.S. newspapers. Due to limited articles for this research, this study limits the generalizability of my findings.

My research focused on the description of media about the prevalence of child marriage by U.S. newspapers. The result of this research shows two critical issues. One, this topic needs to be researched more, especially regarding the prevalence of child marriage in the United States. This study highlighted that most U.S. newspapers ignore the discussion of child marriage in this country. That finding can indicate why many people in this country are not informed about the type of union in the United States. My research also discussed child marriage in Afghanistan, which majority of my available articles (30 articles) discussed this topic. This could be an implication of why most people in this country assume that this practice only takes place in other countries, mainly the Middle East. I feel the rich data that my small number of articles provided me will be helpful to improve the existing literature and might be helpful for future researches done by other scholars. Ultimately, my research is helpful to better understand the role of media in the lack of information and misconception of the public about the prevalence of child marriages.

Future Research

Future research should examine what other factors may lead to child marriage in the United States. Research should also examine child marriage in other states in this country, especially within more conservatives' cities. Furthermore, based on my knowledge, the role of different religions in the prevalence of child marriage in the U.S. was never discussed. Islam is mainly aimed by researchers as the religion which promotes child marriage. Other researches can focus on media framing, messaging, and agenda setting. The ways these messages are strategically constructed also should be examined by other scholars. Researchers should look at other religions and their influence on this phenomenon specifically in the United States. At the same time, it has been noticed that U.S. newspapers are not interested in covering this topic, which directly influences the lives of many children in this country. Future researches should examine why these agencies are hesitant in

covering this topic. The victims of child marriage in the United States are ignored by U.S. media, which may lead to lack of knowledge about this type of union among public. They have been treated as a lost group within society. Further research about the prevalence of child marriage in the United States can bring awareness and knowledge among the public, leading to abolishing this practice in this country.

Conclusion

Based on the result of this study, child marriage in the United States was described as a practice among immigrants and families that try to escape being stigmatized for their teenage daughter's pregnancies. The legal system in the United States is framed for being influenced by religiosity and religious groups. U.S. newspapers also pointed that the legalization of such unions can promote the prevalence of such unions in the United States. Islam, specially shariah law, was pointed out by U.S. news agencies as the cause for the prevalence of child marriage in Afghanistan. They also explained that the interconnection of law and religion in this country does not allow the child marriage law to be implemented and enforced. Lastly, the prevalence of child marriage in India is mainly framed around the culture of poverty. Journalists pointed out extreme poverty, especially in rural areas, leading to the marriage of many children in this country.

REFERENCES

- Abdullah, S. T. & Quayes, S. (2015). The adverse effect of child marriage on women's economic well-being in Bangladesh – can microfinance help? *The Journal of Developing Areas*, 49(4), 109–125. <https://doi.org/10.1353/jda.2015.0148>
- Ahmed, S., Khan, S., Alia, M., & Noushad, S. (2013). Psychological impact evaluation of early marriages. *International Journal of Endorsing Health Science Research*, 1(2), 84–86. <https://doi.org/10.29052/IJEHSR.v1.i2.2013.84-86>
- Ahonsi, B., Fuseini, K., Nai, D., Goldson, E., Owusu, S., Ndifuna, I., Humes, I., & Tapsoba, P. L. (2019). Child marriage in Ghana: Evidence from a multi-method Study. *BMC Women's Health*, 19(1), 126.
- Alissa J. Rubin. (2010). For Afghan wives, a desperate, fiery way out: Foreign desk. *The New York Times*. <https://www.nytimes.com/2010/11/08/world/asia/08burn.html>
- Alissa J. Rubin. (2011). For Afghan woman, justice runs into unforgiving wall of custom: Foreign desk. *The New York Times*. <https://www.nytimes.com/2011/12/02/world/asia/for-afghan-woman-justice-runs-into-the-static-wall-of-custom.html>
- Alissa J. Rubin. (2011). Law and custom press Afghan women's shelters: Foreign desk. *The New York Times*. <https://www.nytimes.com/2011/02/11/world/asia/11shelter.html>
- Alissa J. Rubin. (2013). Painful payment for Afghan debt: A daughter, 6: Foreign desk. *The New York Times*. <https://www.nytimes.com/2013/04/01/world/asia/afghan-debts-painful-payment-a-daughter-6.html>
- Alissa J. Rubin. (2013). Effort to strengthen an afghan law on women may backfire: Foreign desk. *The New York Times*. <https://www.nytimes.com/2013/05/19/world/asia/efforts-to-strengthen-afghan-law-on-women-may-backfire.html>
- Alissa J. Rubin. (2013). Afghan effort to get justice for women seems to stall: Foreign desk. *The New York Times*. <https://www.nytimes.com/2013/12/09/world/asia/justice-for-abused-afghan-women-still-elusive-un-report-says.html>
- Anderson, C. (2010). Presenting and evaluating qualitative research. *American Journal of Pharmaceutical Education*, 74(8), 141.
- Asling-Monemi, K., Tabassum Naved, R., & Persson, L. A. (2008). Violence against women and the risk of under-five mortality: Analysis of community-based data from rural Bangladesh. *Acta Pædiatrica*, 97(2), 226–232. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1651-2227.2007.00597.x>
- Burney, S. (2012). *Pedagogy of the other: Edward Said, postcolonial theory, and strategies for critique*. Peter Lang.
- Banerjee, P. R. (2014). Dowry in 21st-century India. *Trauma, Violence & Abuse*, 15(1), 34–40. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1524838013496334>
- Barnert, E., Iqbal, Z., Bruce, J., Anoshiravani, A., Kolhatkar, G., & Greenbaum, J. (2017). Commercial sexual exploitation and sex trafficking of children and adolescents: A narrative review. *Academic Pediatrics*, 17(8), 825–829. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acap.2017.07.009>

- Batra, R., & Reio, T. G. (2016). Gender inequality issues in India. *Advances in Developing Human Resources*, 18(1), 88–101.
- Barr, H. (n.d.). *Afghanistan has a tougher law on child marriage than Florida*. Human Rights Watch. <https://www.hrw.org/news/2017/10/20/afghanistan-has-tougher-law-child-marriage>
- Bengtsson, M. (2016). How to plan and perform a qualitative study using content analysis. *NursingPlus Open*, 2, 8–14.
- Bengali, S. 2018. *An Indian activist fights in court to help child brides and grooms win their lives back*. Los Angeles Times Communications LLC.
- Blum, R. W., Li, M., Pasha, O., Rao, C., & Natiq, K. (2019). Coming of age in the shadow of the Taliban: Education, child marriage, and the future of Afghanistan from the perspectives of adolescents and their parents. *Journal of Adolescent Health*, 64(3), 370–75.
- Boyce, S. C., Brouwer, K. C., Triplett, D., Servin, A. E., Magis-Rodriguez, C., & Silverman, J. G. (2018). Childhood experiences of sexual violence, pregnancy, and marriage associated with child sex trafficking among female sex workers in two US–Mexico border cities. *American Journal of Public Health*, 108(8), 1049–54.
- Brüggemann, M. (2014). Between frame setting and frame sending: How journalists contribute to news frames. *Communication Theory*, 24(1), 61–82.
- Chatterjee, S. (2019). Child marriage must end; Nearly 1 in 5 girls is wed before she turns 18. Let's think about them this Valentine's Day. *The Los Angeles Times*. <https://www.latimes.com/opinion/op-ed/la-oe-child-marriage-valentines-day-20190214-story.html>
- Crenshaw, K. (1991). Mapping the margins: Intersectionality, identity politics, and violence against women of color. *Stanford Law Review*, 43(6), 1241–1299. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1229039>
- Crary, D. (2016). Stopping child marriage in U.S.; States intensify efforts to curtail the practice for those under 18, virtually all girls. *The Los Angeles Times*.
- De Avila, J; West, M.G. (2017). States weigh curbing marriage for minors. *The Wall Street Journal, Eastern Edition*. Mar 07, <https://www.wsj.com/articles/states-weigh-curbing-marriage-for-minors-1488859461>
- El-Mowafi, I. M., Hammad, M., & Foster, A. (2017). Child brides' knowledge of and attitudes toward emergency contraception: A qualitative study with Syrian refugees in Jordan. *Contraception (Stoneham)*, 96(4), 268–268. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.contraception.2017.07.028>
- Elo, S., Kääriäinen, M., Kanste, O., Pölkki, T., Utriainen, K., & Kyngäs, H. (2014). Qualitative content analysis. *SAGE Open*, 4. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244014522633>
- Erlingsson, C., & Brysiewicz, P. (2017). A hands-on guide to doing content analysis. *African Journal of Emergency Medicine*, 7(3), 93–99. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.afjem.2017.08.001>
- Foderaro, L. W. (2017b). Child marriage is sharply curtailed by New York legislature. *New York Times*, June 9. <https://www.nytimes.com/2017/06/08/nyregion/child-marriage-is-sharply-curtailed-by-new-york-legislature.html>

- Foderaro, L. W. (2017c.) It's legal for 14-Year-Olds to marry. Cuomo disapproves. *New York Times*, Mar 14. <https://www.nytimes.com/2017/03/13/nyregion/a-push-to-restrict-child-marriages-in-new-york.html>
- Franchino-Olsen, H., Chesworth, B. R., Boyle, C., Rizo, C. F., Martin, S. L., Jordan, B., Macy, R. J., & Stevens, L. (2020). The prevalence of sex trafficking of children and adolescents in the United States: A scoping review. *Trauma, Violence & Abuse*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1524838020933873>
- Gage, A. J. (2013). Child marriage prevention in Amhara Region, Ethiopia: Association of communication exposure and social influence with parents/guardians' knowledge and attitudes. *Social Science & Medicine*, *97*, 124–133. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2013.08.017>
- Gettleman, Jeffrey, and Hari Kumar. 2017. India shields child brides from sex: Foreign desk. *New York Times*, Oct 12, <https://www.nytimes.com/2017/10/11/world/asia/india-child-marriage-rape.html>
- Goffman, E., & Bennett, M. B. (1986). *Frame analysis: An essay on the organization of experience* (1st ed.). Northeastern University Press.
- Graneheim, U. H., & Lundman, B. (2004). Qualitative content analysis in nursing research: Concepts, procedures and measures to achieve trustworthiness. *Nurse Education Today*, *24*(2), 105–12.
- Harmon, A., & Blinder, A. (2018, May 17). Delaware has banned marriage under age 18. Other states also consider limits. *New York Times*, May 17. <https://www.nytimes.com/2018/05/17/us/child-marriage-minimum-age-minors.html>
- Hesse-Biber, S. N. (2017). *The practice of qualitative research: Engaging students in the research process* (3rd ed.). SAGE.
- Hicks, D., & Wang, J. (2013). The New York Times as a resource for mode 2. *Science, Technology & Human Values*, *38*(6), 851–77.
- Hong Le, M. T., Tran, T. D., Nguyen, H. T., & Fisher, J. (2014). Early marriage and intimate partner violence among adolescents and young adults in Viet Nam. *Journal of Interpersonal Violence*, *29*(5), 889–910. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0886260513505710>
- Human Rights Watch (2009, December 6). *We Have the promises of the world*. <https://www.hrw.org/report/2009/12/06/we-have-promises-world/womens-rights-afghanistan>
- International Women's Health Coalition (n.d.). *The facts on child marriage*. Retrieved June 6, 2020 from <https://iwhc.org/resources/facts-child-marriage/>
- Kabeer, N., & Khan, A. (2014). Cultural values or universal rights? Women's narratives of compliance and contestation in urban Afghanistan. *Feminist Economics*, *20*(3), 1–24.
- Kargar Jahromi, M., Jamali, S., Rahmanian Koshkaki, A., & Javadpour, S. (2015). Prevalence and risk factors of domestic violence against women by their husbands in Iran. *Global Journal of Health Science*, *8*(5), 175–183. <https://doi.org/10.5539/gjhs.v8n5p175>
- Kidman, R. (2017). Child marriage and intimate partner violence: A comparative study of 34 countries. *International Journal of Epidemiology*, *46*(2), 662–75.

- Kearney, M. W. (2017). *Trusting news project report 2017*. Reynolds Journalism Institute. <https://www.rjionline.org/reporthtml.html>
- Laura King. (2011). Afghan plan puts aid for women at risk; Strict governmental control would weaken shelters for abused women and girls, rights groups say. *The Los Angeles Times*.
- Koski, A., & Heymann, J. (2018). Child marriage in the United States: How common is the practice, and which children are at greatest risk? *Perspectives on Sexual & Reproductive Health*, 50(2), 59–65. <https://doi.org/10.1363/psrh.12055>
- Kohno, A., Techasrivichien, T., Suguimoto, S. P., Dahlui, M., Nik Farid, N. D., & Nakayama, T. (2020). Investigation of the key factors that influence the girls to enter into child marriage: A meta-synthesis of qualitative evidence. *PLOS One*, 15(7), e0235959–e0235959. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0235959>
- Kristof, N. (2017, May 28). 'It was forced on me': Child marriage in the U.S.: Commentary. *New York Times*.
- Lawson, D. W., Lynes, R., Morris, A., & Schaffnit, S. B. (2020). What does the American public know about child marriage? *PLOS ONE*, 15(9), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0238346>.
- Le Strat, Y., Dubertret, C., & Le Foll, B. (2011). Child marriage in the United States and its association with mental health in women. *American Academy of Pediatrics*, 128(3), 524–530.
- Lee-Rife, S., Malhotra, A., Warner, A., & Glinski, A. M. (2012). What works to prevent child marriage: A review of the evidence. *Studies in Family Planning*, 43(4), 287–303. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1728-4465.2012.00327.x>
- Lebni, J. Y., Solhi, M., Fard Azar, F. E., & Farahani, F. K. (2020). Qualitative study of social determinants of child marriage in Kurdish regions of Iran: Evidence for health promotion interventions. *Journal of Education and Health Promotion*, 9, 242. https://doi.org/10.4103/jehp.jehp_332_20
- Li, M., Rao, K., Natiq, K., Pasha, O., & Blum, R. (2018). Coming of age in the shadow of the Taliban: Adolescents' and parents' views toward interpersonal violence and harmful traditional practices in Afghanistan. *American Journal of Public Health*, 108(12), 1688–1694. <https://doi.org/10.2105/AJPH.2018.304697>
- Maswikwa, B., Richter, L., Kaufman, J., & Nandi, A. (2015). Minimum marriage age laws and the prevalence of child marriage and adolescent birth: Evidence from Sub-Saharan Africa. *International Perspectives on Sexual and Reproductive Health*, 41(2), 58–68.
- Mashal, M. (2016, Jul 19). Child Marriage at Issue as an Afghan bride dies. *New York Times*
- Macnamara, J. R. (2005). Media content analysis: Its uses, benefits and best practice methodology. *Asia Pacific Public Relations Journal*, 6(1), 1–34.
- Magnier, M. (2012, Oct 14). The World: Girl's death stirs outrage over rape in India; A teen killed herself after being attacked. Officials' reactions appear to excuse the crime, igniting protest. *Los Angeles Times*
- Margolis, H. (n.d.) *Kyrgyzstan ups fight against child marriage*. Human Rights Watch. <https://www.hrw.org/news/2016/11/21/kyrgyzstan-ups-fight-against-child-marriage>

- Melnikas, A. J., Ainul, S., Ehsan, I., Haque, E., & Amin, S. (2020). Child marriage practices among the Rohingya in Bangladesh. *Conflict and Health*, 14(1), 28. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13031-020-00274-0>
- Mohajan, H. K. (2018). Qualitative research mythology in social science and related subjects. *Journal of Economic Development, Environment and People*, 7(1), 23–48.
- Mourtada, R., Schlecht, J., & DeJong, J. (2017). A qualitative study exploring child marriage practices among Syrian conflict-affected populations in Lebanon. *Conflict and Health*, 11(Sup. 1), 27.
- Nasrullah, M., Zakar, R., Zakar, M. Z., Abbas, S., Safdar, S., Shaukat, M., & Krämer, A. (2014). Knowledge and attitude towards child marriage practice among women married as children—a qualitative study in urban slums of Lahore, Pakistan. *BMC Public Health*, 14, 1148.
- Nguyen, M. C., & Wodon, Q. (2012). Measuring child marriage. *Economics Bulletin*, 32(1), 398–411.
- Nour, N. M. (2006). Health consequences of child marriage in Africa. *Emerging Infectious Diseases*, 12(11), 1644–1649. <https://doi.org/10.3201/eid1211.060510>
- Nordland, R. (2014). Taliban and government imperil gains for Afghan Women, advocates say: Foreign desk. *The New York Times*. <https://www.nytimes.com/2014/02/08/world/asia/womens-rights-seen-as-vulnerable-to-reversal-in-afghanistan.html>
- Nordland, R. (2018). Married to a family torn by war: Foreign desk. *The New York Times*.
- Nordland, R., & Jawad Sukhanyar. (2015). Afghan Mullah leading stoning inquiry condones practice: Foreign desk. *The New York Times*. <https://www.nytimes.com/2015/11/08/world/asia/afghan-mullah-leading-stoning-inquiry-condones-practice.html>
- Nordland, R. & Rubin, A. J. (2010). Escaping marriage, but not lashes: Foreign desk. *The New York Times*. <https://www.nytimes.com/2010/05/31/world/asia/31flogging.html>
- Nwaolikpe, O. N. (2018). Should we keep this quiet? Print media and child marriage in Nigeria. *Global Media Journal*, 16(31), 1.
- Pandya, Y. P., & Bhandari, D. J. (2015). An epidemiological study of child marriages in a rural community of Gujarat. *Indian Journal of Community Medicine*, 40(4), 246–51.
- Paul, P. (2019). Effects of education and poverty on the prevalence of girl child marriage in India: A district-level analysis. *Children and Youth Services Review*, 100, 16–21. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.childyouth.2019.02.033>
- Paul, P., & Mondal, D. (2021). Child marriage in India: A human rights violation during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Public Health*, 33(1), 162–163. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1010539520975292>
- Prasad, B. D. (2019). Qualitative content analysis: why is it still a path less taken? *Forum Qualitative Social Research*, 20(3). <http://dx.doi.org/10.17169/fqs-20.3.3392>
- Qamar, M., Harris, M. A., & Tustin, J. L. (2020). The association between child marriage and domestic violence in Afghanistan. *Journal of Interpersonal Violence*, 88626052095131–886260520951310. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0886260520951310>

- Raj, A., Gomez, C. S., & Silverman, J. G. (2014). Multisectoral Afghan perspectives on girl child marriage: Foundations for change do exist in Afghanistan. *Violence Against Women, 20*(12), 1489–505.
- Raj, A., Saggurti, N., Lawrence, D., Balaiiah, D., & Silverman, J. G. (2010). Association between adolescent marriage and marital violence among young adult women in India. *International Journal of Gynecology and Obstetrics, 110*(1), 35–39. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijgo.2010.01.022>
- Nicholas Riccardi. (2010). The Nation: Jeffs' conviction reversed; The polygamist leader was found guilty in 2007 of being an accomplice to rape. *The Los Angeles Times*.
- Rumble, L., Peterman, A., Irdiana, N., Triyana, M., & Minnick, E. (2018). An empirical exploration of female child marriage determinants in Indonesia. *BMC Public Health, 18*(1), 407.
- Saada, Najwan. (2014). A review of "Pedagogy of the other: Edward Said, postcolonial theory, and strategies for critique" [Review]. *Educational Studies, 50*(6), 605–611. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00131946.2014.963853>
- Saldaña, J. (2016). *The coding manual for qualitative researchers* (3rd ed.). SAGE.
- Salvi, V. (2009). Child marriage in India: A tradition with alarming implications. *The Lancet, 373*(9678), 1826–7.
- Semetko, H. A., & Scammell, M. (2012). *The SAGE handbook of political communication*. SAGE.
- Seth, R., Bose, V., Qaiyum, Y., Chandrashekhar, R., Kansal, S., Taneja, I., & Seth, T. Social determinants of child marriage in Rural India. *Ochsner Journal, 18*(4), 390–394.
- Smith, B., & Searle, J. (2003). The construction of social reality: An exchange. *The American Journal of Economics and Sociology, 62*(1), 285–309. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/3487972>.
- Svanemyr, J., Chandra-Mouli, V., Christiansen, C. S., & Mbizvo, M. (2012). Preventing child marriages: First international day of the girl child "my life, my right, end child marriage." *Reproductive Health, 9*(1), 31–31. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1742-4755-9-31>
- Taefi, N. (2009). The synthesis of age and gender: Intersectionality, international human rights law and the marginalisation of the girl-child. *The International Journal of Children's Rights, 17*(3), 345–376. <https://doi.org/10.1163/157181809X458049>
- Uecker, J. (2014). Religion and early marriage in the United States: Evidence from the Add health study. *Journal for the Scientific Study of Religion, 53*(2), 392–415.
- United States Institute of Peace Organization (2019, February 11). *Fast facts: 10 facts illustrating why we must #EndChildMarriage*. Retrieved June 27, 2020, <https://www.unicef.org/eca/press-releases/fast-facts-10-facts-illustrating-why-we-must-endchildmarriage>
- Van Coller, A. (2017). Child marriage – Acceptance by association. *International Journal of Law, Policy, and the Family, 31*(3), 363–76.
- Warria, A. (2017). Forced child marriages as a form of child trafficking. *Children and Youth Services Review, 79*, 274–79.

Wodon, Q., Nguyen, M. C., & Tsimpo, C. (2016). Child marriage, education, and agency in Uganda. *Feminist Economics*, 22(1), 54–79. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13545701.2015.1102020>

Yale University. (2018). Scholarly vs. popular sources. Retrieved from <https://ctl.yale.edu/writing/using-sources/scholarly-vs-popular-sources>